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GWALIOR STATE

FOR

Samvat 1986, Year 1929-30.

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GWALIOR STATE

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ANNUAL ADMINISTRATION REPORT
OF THE
DEPARTMENT OF ARCHÆOLOGY, GWALIOR STATE
FOR THE
Year ending 30th June 1930, Samvat 1986.

PART I.

I. Office Notes.

Charge.—During the year of report, the undersigned held charge of the Department, except from 30th May to the 30th June, while he was on leave. During the period of leave, the charge of the current duties of the post remained with R. S. Saksena, the Inspector of Archæology.

Leave.—The Superintendent availed himself of one month and nineteen days' privilege leave, inclusive of 13 days *Sutak* leave.

Members of the subordinate staff enjoyed leave as under:—

- (a) *General Assistant.*—37 days' privilege leave at different times.
- (b) *Photographer-Draughtsman.*—Leave without pay for eight months and ten days from the 1st July 1929 to the 10th March 1930.
- (c) *Assistant Photographer-Draughtsman.*—7 days' privilege leave at different times.
- (d) *Curator.*—30 days' privilege and *Sutak* leave combined.
- (e) *Officer Accounts.*—16 days' privilege leave at different times.
- (f) *Officer Correspondence.*—20 days' privilege leave from the 10th to the 30th January 1930.
- (g) *Record Keeper.*—34 days' privilege leave and two days' leave without pay at different times.

Appointments and promotions.—As mentioned in last year's report, the Officer Accounts had to be relieved of his duties on account of his failing health. This post was filled up during the year under report by the appointment of S. V. Dhopatkar, a young and energetic accounts clerk from the Office of the A. O. Agriculture, who very kindly spared him.

V. M. Shavrikar, the assistant photographer-draughtsman, was promoted to the extent of his budgetted pay from 11th March 1930.

General.—All the office staff discharged their respective duties harmoniously, deligently and carefully for which I am glad to record my appreciation.

II. Administrative Changes and Orders.

Circular No. 6, Samvat 1986, Home Department (Section Archæology) was issued in the *Gwalior Government Gazette* of the 5th April 1930. The Circular aims at obtaining co-operation of the general public in the field of archæological exploration and provides for the appreciation and reward of the services of persons who may give information of such monuments, inscriptions, or other antiquities as being of archæological or historical interest may not be on the list of the Archæological Department. How far the encouragement held out will serve to dispel the apathy in the general public towards archæological and historical research and how many monuments and antiquities will thus be saved from undeserved oblivion or destruction, experience alone will show.

The growing activities of the Archæological Department especially in the branches of conservation and exploration had long since created the necessity of the provision of an act for the due protection and care of the monuments and antiquities in the State as the existing Circulars had proved inadequate to serve this end. A draft of such an act based on the lines of Government of India Act VII of 1904 (Ancient Monuments Preservation Act) was therefore, prepared and submitted to the Home Member in Samvat 1983, for consideration. Thanks to his efforts and the whole-hearted sympathy of the Council of Regency, the Act was duly passed after certain minor modifications in the original draft and came into operation in the year of report by an announcement and publication of the Act in the *Gwalior Government Gazette*, dated 21st June 1930.

III. Work at Headquarters.

In addition to the ordinary Office routine the following work was done during the headquarter season:—

- (a) An Annual Administration Report for Samvat 1985 was drawn up and submitted.
- (b) An Album of important photographs taken during the year of report was prepared and submitted.
- (c) New acquisitions of antiquities in the Museum were classified, arranged and labelled.
- (d) The coins received as treasure-trove finds or offered for sale and exchange by Institutions and private bodies were examined and disposed.
- (e) A revised 4th edition of the Gwalior Fort Album was brought out.
- (f) The brochure *Archæology in Gwalior* having run out of stock was revised and brought up-to-date, for distribution in a short form on the occasion of the session of Indian Historical Records Commission at Gwalior and further developed for final publication in an enlarged form.
- (g) A Map of Gwalior State showing important places of Archæological interest upto the end of Samvat 1986 with necessary road and rail communications was completed.

- (h) An album containing illustrations and short notes of the Surwaya antiquities was published.
- (i) An article on Bagh caves published in the Indian State Railway Magazine was adopted for a separate issue in pamphlet form for visitors as the monograph on the caves has gone beyond the reach of general public on account of its high price.
- (j) An article on the general condition of the Bagh Caves and specially the work done by the Gwalior Government regarding their preservation was published in the daily issue of the 'Statesman' and the 'Indian Daily Mail' with a view to remove the wrong impression about the caves, which found its way in the report of a lecture by Principal Mukul Day of the School of Arts, Calcutta, published in the 'Statesman'.
- (k) Another illustrated article on the Bagh Caves in Hindi was contributed to the special birthday issue of the local paper the "Jayaji Pratap".
- (l) An article on the memorial of Mahadji Scindia and the Chhatri of Maharani Lakshmibai of Jhansi was contributed to the special Art Supplement of the Indian States Journal of Bombay.
- (m) Out of the three edited Persian Inscriptions from Bhilsa two were contributed to the Epigraphia Indo-Moslemica and one to the Indian Historical Quarterly, Calcutta.
- (n) Short screen lectures were delivered at different Ganesh Mandals at Lashkar.
- (o) Enlarged photographs of important archæological monuments were prepared, framed and exhibited at certain Dak Bungalows in the State, in the vicinity of which the important monuments lay, with a view to arouse the interest of travellers to go and visit the monuments.

IV. Tours.

During the year of report, the Superintendent spent 68 days in camp, partly for annual inspection of monuments already conserved, for directing and supervising the conservation works in progress, and partly for listing of monuments. The Offg. Superintendent also toured for 18 days for a similar purpose. The detailed tour diary will be found in Appendix A.

The Superintendent paid visits of annual inspection to the monuments at Antri, Surwaya, Narwar, Ranod, Chanderi, Badoh, Udaypur, Bhilsa, Udaygiri, Ujjain, Mandasor and Sondni. He supervised and directed the conservation works in progress at Padhavli, Gwalior, Besnagar and Bagh, and the excavation works at Chanchoda. He drew up conservation notes devising measures of repairs to monuments at Kherhat, Ater and Suhania. He visited 36 places in different districts of the State for listing of monuments and taking notes on Fort.

The Offg. Superintendent visited Padhavli to direct the conservation in progress, and the following places for listing of monuments:—

Nurabad, Amrol, Dhonwa, Dandekikhidak, Jakhoda, Khudaoli and Chanderi.

V. Conservation.

During the year of report conservation of ancient monuments was carried out at Padhavli (District Tonwarghar), Lashkar (District Gird), Besnagar (District Bhilsa) and at Bagh (District Amjhera). As the non-recurring grant proposed in the budget for Samvat 1986 was not sanctioned, the conservation activities were limited to the small recurring grant availed for this purpose in the regular budget. The list of monuments conserved and the amounts spent on these works, is shown in Appendix B.

Padhavli (District Tonwarghar).—The monuments treated here is the remnant of a beautiful temple of the 10th Cent. A. D. which had to be reclaimed from the womb of a fortress which sprang on it in later times. The work of conserving this monument was started as early as V. S. 1982.

The Annual Report for that year contains notes on the general condition and description of the monument. But in view of other more important works requiring urgent attention, sufficient funds could not be spared for the completion of this work at one stretch. The work is therefore being pushed on gradually year after year as will appear from the annual reports of this Department, for the last four years. From the available grant in the year of report the following items were executed:—

1. The accretions and fillings round the temple were excavated and removed to the extent necessary for exposing the plinth of the main temple and the original pavement in front. The accretions in some places consisted of pucca masonry walls which were dismantled and taken off. In places the fillings were mixed with heavy blocks of stone which were removed with some difficulty.
2. Masonry breast walls were then built up to stop the slips of the edges of debris and accretions which had thus been cut up.
3. Portions of the pavement of the *Sabhamandapa* had been disturbed. They were properly relaid, missing slabs being supplied.
4. Petty repairs in cut-stone were done to the walls of the temple.
5. Disturbed ceiling stones and panels of sculptures were reset in position and all the carvings and sculptures were freed from rubbish filling and obscuring them for centuries. Some work still awaits being done here in the next year.

Lashkar (District Gird).—Chhatri of Maharani Lakshmi Bai of Jhansi the conservation of which was completed in Samvat 1985, attracts a good number of visitors on account of its prominent situation which made it necessary to keep a whole time care-taker on the spot to keep the monument clean and protect the same from vandalism. The care-taker thus appointed was required to live at the site and so a temporary quarter was built for him during the year of report. Besides one of the inscribed tablets on the chhatri which had broken was replaced. Also name panels both in English and Hindi on gate posts were added for guidance of

passers-by. The procedure for the acquisition of land round the chhatri having completed, compensation for the same was also paid during the year of report.

Besnagar (District Bhilsa).—Two miles north-west of Bhilsa Station along the Bhilsa-Samshabad road stands the most ancient and important archæological monument in the State namely the *Heliodoros Pillar*, locally called *Khambaba*. The monument is situated in the compound of the house of a Babaji who is a farmer and keeps a number of cattle. To save the monument from these rural friends, a stone and bar railing was provided some years ago along with the conservation of the monument. But the railing proved too weak to withstand the attacks of the unconscious vandals—the quadrupeds—and gave way several times. This railing had therefore to be replaced with a new one made up of stronger stone posts and pipes in places of bars. A care-taker has also been appointed recently to look after the Bhilsa monuments. He is charged with the further safe-guarding of this valuable relic and keeping the premises neat and tidy. With a view to free the monument of this sort of recurring trouble, operations for the acquisitions of the land round the monument for the Archæological Department have been started.

In response to a proposal of this Department, the P. W. Department constructed in the year of report a pucca approach road to the Heliodoros pillar which being one of the most interesting monuments in the State attracts even distant foreign visitors. This road will greatly facilitate the visits of highclass travellers. A long-felt want has thus been supplied for which our thanks are due to the P. W. D.

Bagh (District Amjhera).—The group of Buddhist Caves at Bagh are too wellknown to need an introduction here. Measures of clearance and some very urgent repairs have been executed here in the past few years. Being the premier monument in this State and being in the urgent need of repairs, a comprehensive estimate for this work has been for some time under the consideration of the Council of Regency. As no sanction for a special grant for this purpose was received in the year of report, some emergent work only was carried out from the current year's ordinary budget grant, the items thus executed being:—

1. Decayed rock in certain places was chiselled off.
2. Such portions of pillars of walls as were in immediate danger of peeling or falling off were repaired in cut-stone masonry.

VI. Annual Up-keep.

Annual clearance and petty repairs were carried out to all important groups of monuments already conserved.

VII. Exploration

(a) Excavations.

No proper excavation could be taken up this year, as the monuments above ground, whose conservation was incomplete has a prior claim in the available funds. However a trial excavation was tried at Chanchoda.

Chanchoda is a small town and headquarters of a Tehsil in District Esagarh of the State. A two miles branch road connects this town with the Agra-Bombay trunk road at Benagaon, a small Mandi about 180 miles south of Gwalior. Chanchoda is said to have been founded by Khichi Rajputs probably in the 18th century when their capital was in the stronghold at Bajrangarh and possesses a small fort (now ruined) on a small hillock. There are no ruins of antiquarian interest except the remains of a small shrine of the mediæval times and a piece of monolithic pillar. The latter is a portion of a sixteen sided pillar of reddish sandstone 2' 2" in diameter with a socket hole in its top which is apparently entire. When it was first examined it was standing upright on the north bank of the Chanchoda tank projecting nearly 3 feet above ground. Tradition described it as a *lat* marking the site of a big hidden treasure whose exposure was attended with tremendous perils and bad consequences. To the archæologists, however, it was beyond doubt a portion of an old monolithic column such as were erected in front of temples or stupas and its examination promised clue to some historical inscription on the column itself or exposing the remains of a connected monument. So when the water level of the tank fell to its lowest in the hot season the ground round the shaft was excavated carefully and carried a few feet below the bottom of the shaft. But the attempt carried us no further. It was found that the pillar 6' 7" long was a piece of the shaft of a column while lower portion was missing and thus it was not standing on its original site. How and whence it came here could not be traced.

(b) Listing of Monuments.

One hundred and thirty-four Monuments situated at 43 different places in the districts of Amjhera, Bhilsa, Bhind, Esagarh, Gird, Mandasor, Narwar, Shajapur and Tonwarghar, were listed in the year of report.

District Amjhera.

Amjhera.—This place has already been explored in past years. This visit was made especially to take notes about the fort, in connection with an order of the Home Member Sahib to compile a descriptive list of the forts and *gadhis* in the State.

The fort stands on the west bank of the tank. It is built of rubble stone and brick in lime and consists of two adjacent court-yards. A gate in the west wall gives access to the outer enclosure. After passing through the outer court one enters the inner court by a gate in the south wall. The outer enclosure contained horse stables and servant quarters which are now in total ruins, and the more important residential buildings are situated in the inner court now occupied by the Distillery and its staff.

Two of the buildings are three storeyed and the rest two storeyed.

The chief feature of interest about this fort worth-noticing is that that there are some rural paintings decorating the third storey of the main building. They depict scenes of Darbar and Shikar of Rajput kings and feats of acrobats etc. Unfortunately the walls are now white-washed

with the result that the paintings are obliterated; but the wash can perhaps be removed and at least some of the paintings reclaimed. There is also an old gun 7' 9" long with an aperture $4\frac{3}{4}$ " in diameter.

District Bhilsa.

Bhilaya.—The village lies 6 miles east of Udaypur about 18 miles from Basoda by direct route. The place was visited in consequence of a report to the effect that an inscription had been unearthed there during farming operation by Mr. Patel, the Zamindar of the place. The village stands at the slope of a low hill and claims no antiquities. The inscription under reference turned out on examination to be an inscribed Sati stone which originally stood at the spot, and fell prostrate in course of time and was exposed again while digging earth for the repair of the earthen dam of the adjoining tank. Close to the above Sati, under a tamarind tree, stood another Sati-stone which also is inscribed. The inscription on the prostrate pillar is dated in V. S. 1392 and that on the standing one is dated in V. S. 1393. Both refer to the reign of Sultan Mahmud or probably Muhammad Tughalaq of Delhi (*Vide* Nos. 1 and 2 of Appendix D.) and both have the usual sculptures.

Udaypur.—Outside the Motia Gate of the town stands a small mosque in Mandu style. It was noticed last year and is described in last year's report. It was examined again this year to verify the inscription on the spot as the impressions were not clear enough.

District Bhind.

Ater.—The place was visited this year again with a view to check the notes on the fort taken previously and to add such as were necessary for being embodied in the proposed History of Forts. A fresh monument noticed here this time is a well near the temple inside the fort. It has an inscription in Hindi cut in raised letters, recording the construction of the well by one of the kings (*Vide* No. 5 of Appendix D). Further it came to notice on close examination that the temple is a later conversion of what was originally a part of Mahal. This is indicated among other proofs by the fact that the marble tread stones of the steps leading the temple have been taken promiscuously from the marble in front. There are two cisterns in between the Dewankhana or Dewan-i-Khas and the marble flooring. On the back of the Dewankhana is a large open air double platform with a raised seat or throne in the west wall. Probably a spacious *shamiana* tent was set up here when necessary and used as a Dewan-i-Am.

Bara.—It is a fairly large village and is situated on a low earthen mound which had at one time a Gadhi of earthen walls. It lies about six miles to the north-west of Rithora Kalan Railway Station and is better known on account of the lower head works on the Sank Asan main canal located here. Some ancient ruins lie within the precincts of the village.

Outside the village, towards the north, stand a few ruined shrines. One of these is a shrine facing east near what was once a tank. It stands on a plinth about eight feet high above ground of which the inner core

only is preserved. The *sikhara* and porch are fallen away. The door frame exists *in situ* and has Vishnu as the central figure on its lintel. But inside is what appears to have been a pedestal supporting a *Siva Linga* now no more. On the outer face of walls are Ganesa in the south, Surya in the west and Kartikeya in the north.

Nearby lie an old well with a one piece stone trough. Further north lie remnants of two more shrines, one of which retained part of walls. Close to these is another old round well the lower portion of which is built of small stone masonry and the upper portion of large blocks and a one piece stone trough placed beside.

Close to the village, towards the north-east about a hundred feet of the track lie half buried in a field four memorial pillars. The top panel of each one shows a bust whose hair is in the form of a wig. The lower panels of sculpture show the usual scenes of fight etc. In one or two are cows suckling their calves. Pieces of two more pillars are lying on the site. These are locally called Joginis.

Further-on in a field along a canal distributary running in a north-ernly direction are two Sati-stones with the usual sculpture. One of these is lying and bears an inscription dated V. S. 1487, which is illegible in other respects.

Bara Kalan.—It is a good village about five miles on the road to Bhandar. Near the village are seen the ruins of probably two Vishnu temples lying flanking the road. The original temples, it seems were of bricks decorated with stone carvings, as the site is studded with brick bats. The brick mounds seem to have been exploited for house building by the villagers as very little of the material now survives on the spot. However what is left of the stone carvings is a high class relic of the sculptor's art and may be as old as the 7th or 8th century A D. The surviving pieces consist of two complete door jambs, fragments of another door frame, two lintels, one sil and a torso of an idol of god all belonging to Vishnu temples.

Devala—It is a small village a mile and a half west of Ater, and not of very old standing. It derives its name from a Devalaya of a temple in the village said to have been built by a Bhadauria Raja, which is now in ruins. The only object noticed here is an interesting Sati monument on a platform outside village by the side of the foot-path from Ater to Devala. There is no clear inscription on the monuments. The exact name of the Raja is not known. This much, however, is certain that he was one of the Bhadauria Rulers of Ater, whose descendants still enjoy a Jagir at Nayagaon, District Etawah, and come to worship the Sati on certain occasions

The carved slab measures 6' x 2' and is built up in brick and lime work. The sculpture is peculiar. The Raja is shown seated on a throne in the centre. To the right of Raja are carved two rows of females and a sun in the corner. The upper row represents attendants carrying *chowri* and fan while in the lower row are musicians playing on tabor, guitar and cymbals. To the left of the Raja is seated the Rani who be-

came Sati. She is sitting in a peculiar pose with face turned towards the Raja and holds a coconut in her hand. There is a sword under her feet. She is also attended by two rows of females. The upper row represents attendants who carry in their hands a *chowri*, a *surahi* (jar) and a cup. The moon is represented in one top corner and the sun on its opposite. In the lower row are six lady musicians three of whom are playing on the *sitar*, the cymbal and the tabor respectively, while the remaining are dancing and singing. Opposite this row on the left are five musicians, one holding *khadtal* and the rest are dancing. There is a line of inscription on the left hand corner but is too much worn-out to be made out.

Another slab of about the same size as the one just described stands on ruined platform adjoining the above. The general design is also very similar but the carving is only in shallow outline.

Gohad.—This was visited again in the year of report in order to enquire further about the Christian tombs examined last year (*Vide* Annual Report for Samvat 1985). No more tombs could be traced. The only new piece of information was that the tombs are locally called *Goras*, i. e., tombs of *Gora log* (white Europeans). Lambert's tomb near the Dak Bungalow is called Burraka Gora, and the two other are called Gohadika Gora and Bannipuraka Gora respectively.

Gohadi.—This village possesses besides the Christian tomb already known, the site of an old temple, a worn-out sculpture of Kubera and a Sati pillar with the usual sculpture lying prostrate. All these are by the side of the cart-track from Gohad. The Christian tomb here which is faced with stone slabs is the most preserved of all such tombs in the vicinity of Gohad.

District Bajrangarh (Esagarh).

Bajrangarh.—The place has been explored in past years. It was visited again this year to examine the Bisbhujia Devi's temple which still remained to be listed and also to take additional notes on the Fort.

The fort of Bajrangarh as noticed before has been built by Khichi Rajputs in the 17th century. Nothing beyond tradition has survived to support the assertion. Another tradition asserts that the fort was originally built by a people of *Ber Gadia* caste now extinct and was improved later on by the Khichi Rajput conquerors who also built forts at Raghogarh, Maksudangarh, Narsingharh and Khilchipur, besides many other small fortresses in the Khichiwada or the country round Bajrangarh. The building in the fort known as Mahal is said to have been built in 1852. The fort was captured by Baptist Filose in V. S. 1872, for Scindia, in the time of Jaisingh the last ruling Rajput prince of Bajrangarh.

The Bisbhujia Devi temple is a small modern shrine and stands on a low hill about a mile to the south west of the town. The whole building is a two storeyed one. The ground flat is a Dharmashala. The shrine proper and some other subsidiary buildings are on the upper storey. The

shrine has a fluted dome for its *sikhar*, a pillared porch and *pradakshina* path the whole perched on a small platform facing north. On its left or west is an old mediæval shrine with a cell and porch now in ruins. The sculpture of goddess, an eighteen armed Mahishamardini now worshipped in the modern temple appears to be the broken idol taken from the old temple. The idol is now repaired and finished with oil paint, red body, green *sari* and yellow *choli* (vest). She is accompanied by two female attendants. There is under the feet of the goddess the body of a buffalo. The detached head of the buffalo now present is an earthen object, the original one of stone having been originally lost.

On another platform at the back of the shrine are the 11th and 12th century images of Bhairava and nine other goddesses namely, (1) Parvati standing, (2) Indrani seated, (3) Vaishnavi seated on Garuda, (4) Kali seated, (5) Brahmani seated, (6) an unknown goddess seated on horse, (7) Kaumari, (8) Mahesvari and (9) Varahi. Close-by is lying an old sculptured lintel having on it in the centre Siva dancing accompanied by five goddesses and Ganesa playing on different instruments of music. The temple is provided with lighting pyramids (Dipamalikas) three on back and two in front as well as two *baradoaries* (halls) and Nagarkhana. A two line Nagari inscription on the metal bell records that it is a gift from Kondo Krishna Limaye in V. S. 1944. There is also a recent scribing with charcoal on the temple by some visitor recording that the temple was built by one Jaimangalsingh (?) of Raghogarh. This writing is quite modern but it may have preserved an old tradition.

Close the hill is an old site which is said to have yielded old bricks and stones of Jaina temples now built into modern Jaina temples in the town of Bajrangarh.

Chanchoda.—This is a large village, two miles by road from Binagaon Dak Bungalow on the Agra-Bombay trunk road, about 185 miles south of Gwalior. The place possesses a few monuments of archæological interest such as the piece of shaft of an old column dealt under 'Excavations' (p. 5) above, a ruined old shrine and a small ruined fort.

The town itself does not appear of long founding and probably grew up only under the Khichi Rajputs who are said to have built the small fort here. The fort stands on a small hill on the west of the town, was protected by many strong bastions and had a number of residential buildings of the Rajput type. But they are all now in ruins. There is in the fort also a chhatri of a Gosai named Bhimgir, which bears a Hindi inscription recording that it was built by Mahraja Sri Vikramajit (Vide No. 9 of Appendix D.). Another small hillock close-by is shown as the site of an old fortress called *Phuta Qila* or ruined fort.

Among other objects of general interest here may be mentioned (1) The tank, (2) Bagajesvar Mahadeva temple which is situated in the midst of charming natural scenery. (3) The chhatri of Sersinghji and (4) Ranioki Baodi.

Chanderi.—The place has been fully explored in the past years. It was visited twice in the year of report. Once for annual inspection of the conserved monuments and for the second time in response to a report of the care-taker about an inscription. This inscription has already been noticed in V. S. 1971, but it attracted notice simply as the care-taker reported about it under different name and was thought to be a new one.

Further enquiries were carried about the tomb of Captain Keatings who fell here in 1858 and was buried on the fort. During the inspection of the fort two strayed tombs built of rubble stones and lime were pointed out. One is on the Gilua Tal, lies north and south and has a lamp post at its head and is evidently a muhammadan one.

The other tomb shown is under a tamarind tree near a chhatri closed to the point where the passage begins to descent to the Jogesvari temple. The present tomb is only a platform $10\frac{1}{2}'$ long, $6\frac{1}{2}'$ broad and 3' high. It was perched on a bigger platform or enclosed with a compound wall the debris of which lie scattered round it. The tomb lies in east and west direction after the Christian custom no doubt, but no cross or post at its head now. It has however, a masonry base-mark at its head which must have a cross or some inscription. Its close proximity to the point of Keatings' escalade further supports the surmise that it is the tomb of a Captain Keatings. Careful clearance round the tomb might clear the point still further.

Another object brought to notice was low depression on the fort near the road to the Rest house. It is believed to mark a tank (now silted up) named *Jor Talai* or *Johar Tal* so called, it is said, on account of the Rajput ladies of Medaini Rai having performed Johar on its bank, when he went to fight his last battle with Babar in 1527.

A third monument which came to light this time is a Christian tomb inside the city. It lies in the interior near the city wall about half a furlong to the west of the Delhi gate. The tomb is built of rubble stones under a *Khirni* tree and is now enveloped in jungle. It measures $9' \times 5\frac{1}{2}' \times 2'$ and has a slab stuck up at its eastern end on which is incised in relief a cross. The tomb is a Christian one beyond doubt, the only irregularity being that the cross is set up on the east instead of its usual place on the west. This discrepancy is possible also owing to the fact that the slab is lossed and might have been wrongly planted afterwards. Nothing is known about the inmate of the tomb.

Fatehgarh.—It is a small town reduced to a village about 26 miles by road to south-west of Guna. The only monument worth examination is the fort, said to have been built up by kings of the Khichi Rajputs line who reigned at Bajrangarh. The name of the builder is not known. The fort neither possesses any building of special architectural or historical interest nor has any inscription. Fortifications and other structures here are built up of rubble stone in lime. There are many marks of bombardment. The fort has captured by the Marathas along with Bajrangarh, Raghogarh and Rampur forts.

At present the local police station is housed in the fort and the three storeyed building called Kachcheri is used as quarters of the Police Sub-Inspector.

Rampur.—It is about 30 miles by road to the south-west of Guna being connected by branch road to the Guna-Fatehgarh road. Construction of a big irrigation reservoir near this town in the recent year, and the abundance of good cultural land has attracted some Bombay agriculturists who carried on husbandary on scientific lines with agricultural machinery. Some old sculptures are built up in the dam of a tank.

The place was visited to examine its fort. The fort stands picturesquely on the west bank of a *Nala*, there being a ghat to reach it from the fort. As usual is in this locality, the fort is built up of rubble stone and lime. There are a number of residential buildings in the fort. But they are in total ruins and nothing of particular interest has survived. A few fragmentary sculptures are kept leaning against the outer face of the west wall among which are images of Siva and Parvati, and Seshasayi Vishnu.

Nothing is known of the builders of the fort except the tradition that Khichi Chohans of Bajrangarh took it from Shamraj *Tagore* after the latter was killed. In the interior of the fort a gate is still pointed out where the warrior met his death and some sort of worship is offered here to the memory of the departed soldier. It is one of the twelve forts captured by John Baptist for the Marathas in V. S. 1872, other noticeable forts captured being Bajrangarh, Fatehagarh and Chanchoda in Gwalior State and Chhabra and Gugor in the Tonk State

A tradition is also current of the queen of Jaisingh who was a devoted worshipper of Lord Krishna and who was killed by her own man as she refused to flee away with her royal husband at the last moment of the battle as worship she had been performing had not been yet finished.

A somewhat damaged inscription was found in the inner face of the principle (north east) gate. The inscription is a magic square consisting of nine sub squares. The local people believe it to be an efficacious spell. They say that the cattle passing through the gate under this spell are immune from disease.

District Gird.

Amrol.—It is a good village about ten miles to the north-west of Antri Railway Station. It possesses some ruins of interest as described below:—

1. *Dana-Baba-ki-Marhi.*—This is a ruined Hindu temple of the 11th Century about a furlong to the west of the village. It has lost its *Sikhar* and porch both, a portion of walls of the shrine room is standing. The temple faced north and was dedicated to Siva as a lingam and Nandi are lying closed by and worn-out sculptures of Ganesa and Parvati are among the decorations on the walls. The surviving structure measures $13\frac{1}{2}' \times 14\frac{1}{2}'$ on plan.

Besides the cart-track to the above monument, on a platform under a pipal tree, are heaped fragments of sculptures among which more than one images of seated Jaina Tirthamkaras may be seen.

2. On the northern skirts of the village is another group of ruins. On the foot-path to the above passage are (a) a modern Mata temple, (b) a blind well and (c) a modern room called *Asthan*. In each of these are seen fragments of old worn-out sculptures lying loose or stuck up in the walls.
3. One of the ruins called Ganesa Pahadi is a mound covered with brick bats and probably marks the site of a temple now extinct. It is so named probably after a sculpture of Ganesa $2\frac{1}{2}' \times 3\frac{1}{4}'$ high, placed vertically almost in the centre of mound and resting against a piece of broken female sculpture, which though now broken might have been equal to that of Ganesa when complete. Close to it are lying a torso of a larger male sculpture and two dwarf pillars which are interesting on account of their having human faces and heads with plated hair carved in relief near their tops. At the eastern foot of the mound lies a tall but much damaged sculpture of Kali (skeleton form) broken in three pieces.
4. Just opposite this mound and a furlong to the west of it is the other group of ruins. The group consists of a temple, loose sculptures and some 15 lingams stuck up in the ground, the whole covering an area $150' \times 150'$ enclosed by low brush wood and a few trees, and strewn over with brick bats.

The lingas are all plain but of fair dimensions. The biggest one planted on a modern *chabutra*, measures $2\frac{1}{2}' \times 2\frac{1}{2}' \times 5'$. Curiously enough no debris are left at the site to indicate the number of smaller shrines to which these lingas belonged or to know the exact purpose of the presence of so many lingas. Some excavations may perhaps yield the desired explanation.

Among the loose sculptures may be seen four Nandis, a torso of a big sculpture, two or three smaller sculptures, and a prostrate Sati stone without any inscription.

The temple stands close to the north-east corner of this area and is well preserved except that a part of *sikhar* is gone and has been replaced by a modern cupola of brick and lime in later times. The shrine room in the interior measures $7\frac{1}{2}' \times 7\frac{1}{2}'$ while the outer measurements are $16' \times 9\frac{1}{2}'$. The temple faces east and probably had no porch at all. The temple shelters no particular idol at present though a loose linga and three female images and two other fragments rest in a disorderly manner against the back wall inside the shrine room. The temple appears to be fairly ancient and might be assigned to 8-9th century on account of its carving and sculpture. It differs in some details from the 10-11th century temples. For example the door frame has no dedicatory block but has a frieze of Chaitya medallions in its place. In the centre of the lintel is however a damaged figure resembling Garuda. The lower sculptures on the door jambs are almost hidden and so is the case with the plinth of the temple as the debris have accumulated upto the sill level of the temple.

On the outer faces of temple above plinth is a band of sculptures in which may be seen Ganesa, Parvati, Kaumari and a few dwarf and nude male and female figures.

Churli.—This is a hamlet half a mile to the south of the Tekanpur irrigation dam on the Gwalior Jhansi Road. About two furlongs to the east of the village is a piece of waste and probably the site of an old town possibly dated between the 8th and 11th centuries, covered with brick bats and potsherds and having fragmentary sculptures and other ruins described below:—

Half a mile to the south-east of the village stands a Jaina chaumukha. On the pedestal on each of its four sides are two lions seated, facing away from each other with a wheel or Dharma chakra between. In panels next above are four seated images of Jainas out of which one can be identified as Parsvanath from the serpent seat and canopy. The canopies of the remaining three are in the form of Bengal roofs with foliage decoration. The portion next above is sixteen-sided, further next is eight-sided and ends with circular cone at the top. At four corners of the sixteen-sided portion are four garland bearers. Between each pair of garland bearers is a *mir danga* with two hands (only) playing on each.

There are two courses of leaf decoration and a beaded rosary-like ornament between them in the sixteen-sided portion. It measures 2'2" square at the base and is 7'2" high.

Near-by is lying the lower half of a small sculpture with an attendant on the right. Three sites of Siva temples which are marked by the presence of Siva lingas lie one to the east, a second to the south and a third to the north of the Jaina chaumukha.

Near the northern site are lower fragments of two sculptures of Mahishamardini, an upper fragment of a goddess and a Naga image coiled up. The linga here also had a face. The style of sculptures is early mediæval if not Gupta.

A terra-cota image of a seated goddess lying loose on a mound was picked up and removed to the Archæological Museum. The surviving wallings of a brick temple on this site, are built of large sized old bricks

Bhander.—This place was also visited for the second time. The only information brought to notice are a few relics of the Muhammadan saint Gaffoor popularly known Baba Kapur of Gwalior. The saint is said to have originally lived at Bhander and one Wahid-ud-din, son of Muhammad Latif claims himself as a descendant of saint's family and in support of his assertion he produced two Shahi sanads by virtue of which he still enjoys some of the land in Muafi which was once granted to the saint under the Mughals. Apart from his own claims, he produced certain relics of the saint himself which are described here as a matter of interest though the readers may take the description for what it is.

One of the objects is a bundle of grey hair alleged to be of the saint himself, though it cannot be said that they are of beard or of the head. Another object is a rosary of black glass beads. A third and most interest-

ing object is a piece of fine patti or cotton tape in which a verse from the Quran is very dexteriously woven (black letters on a white field). The tape itself is a fine specimen of fabric of those days.

Baba Kapur whose tomb is at Gwalior and who is very widely venerated is said to have lived at Bhandar for fifty years before he went over to Gwalior. He was a mystic and helped those who sought his aid in distress. His name is still invoked by labourers and cartmen when they are set on a difficult piece of work or at the beginning of the day's work.

Dundapura.—This village is three miles by foot-path to the north-east of Pawa, one of the many shooting resorts which lie to the south-west of Lashkar. Dundapura is also reached by cart-track from Panihar Railway Station whence it is about eight miles nearly west of it.

The present owner of the village, Mr Jagtap on hearsay it seems, reported that there were some old images and caves in a hill near the village, which fact led to the inspection of the place.

The village appears to have been a flourishing one, a hundred years back as testified by originally well built but unfortunately now desolate houses, a big Haveli and a good modern temple of Rama both built by the former Rajput Zamindars. The village stands on a slope of a hill, on the border of a dense jungle full of wild beasts, over-looking the Sankh river (on the east), the situation being very picturesque when the river is flooded during the rains.

The place seems to be inhabited for the last 800-900 years. For there are on the bank of the river at least three uninscribed memorial pillars of warriors killed in battle, about the 10-11th century A. D.

Next there are also the ruins of a small Siva temple of which, the platform, a few carved beams, and 4 or 5 Siva lingas are all that remain. Close-by are the ruins of a Jaina temple. The idol is a seated Jaina which is now lying outside the temple appears to date from the 11th century. The building which is built of small stone masonry with frames, etc., carved in big stones is surely later. The style of carving on the door frames being not earlier than the 15th century. The shrine had disappeared, the *Sabha Mandapa* and porch remains with two door frames, one leading to the shrine and the other to the hall. One of the pillars of this temple has a short pilgrim's record dated V. S. 1598 (?).

A mile to the north of the village on a boulder of rock in the bed of the river a few shallow letters in crude Deva Nagari characters have been carved among which a date may be read as V. S. 1572 (?).

No caves exist in the neighbourhood. I was shown a *Kho* in the deep jungle very difficult of access about two miles to the south-west of the village, what appears to have been once a sort of natural cavern, and now the very home of tigers and other wild beasts.

Dande-ki-khidak.—It is a small village about ten miles south-west of Ghatigaon on the Agra Bombay Road or the Gwalior Light Railway Station Naunanda. To the north of the village near the foot of the hill called Khandilie ruins of group of 11th or 12th century shrines among which a

few fragments of sculptures are seen. Close to this on a small mound is lying a Sati stone dated V. S. 1454. Similar ruins but still more fragmentary lie about two furlongs further in the jungle. These ruins are practically of no interest as they are too meagre to describe. The only thing to be noticed is that these are termed locally as Rathas or chariots on account of the fallen circular slabs (*Amala silas*) of sikhar lying close to them which the rustics take for wheels of chariots.

Jakhoda.—This village lies about one mile and one half to the south east of Dande-ki-khidak. It seems to have been of some standing as there is a ruined Gadhi on the hill overlooking the village. But no ruins of importance were met with here. There are a few inscribed Sati-stones of the 15th and 16th centuries and very fragmentary ruins of a Siva temple to the north of village. Close to it lies prostrate a crude sati-stone with an inscription now almost completely effaced. The village is populated by Gujar Thakurs.

Khudaoli.—Two furlongs to the east of Jakhoda village or on the other side of the hill of Jakhoda lies a waste land where some ruined habitations mark the site of this now deserted village. Here are, also, seen three groups of fragmentary ruins of 12th century temples in an advanced stage of decay and are known as Rathas as mentioned under Dande-ki-khidak village. One old blind well is also situated near the ruins.

Sujwaya.—Deo-kho is a picturesque shikar resort about 11 miles by road to the south-west of Lashkar. $1\frac{1}{2}$ miles to the west of Deo-kho stands a village Malipura, close to which lie a number of ruins of Hindu and Jaina temples. But these ruins practically lie within the limits of Sujwaya, another village a mile further of Malipura. This latter village is said to have been once an adjunct of Sujwaya. This is corroborated by the word pura so called as a handful of Malis once maintained small gardens on the fertile plots with the abundant water supply on either bank of the Nala flowing in this small ravine. The traces of the enclosures of the now extinct gardens are still visible though many of these have since been turned into fields for dry farming.

On the slope of a hill to the north of Malipura is a larger group of ruins. One of the temples, the northern most one, was sacred to Siva, as the lower fragment of the enshrined idol is still lying in the carved debris. It was a representation of Siva and Parvati seated on Nandi and Lion with Ganesa and Kartikeya. Among other sculptures are Ganesa and Surya. Two large ceiling slabs with large lotus flowers carved on them are lying here.

The other temples were dedicated to Jaina Tirthamkaras. About two dozen mutilated images of these Tirthamkaras, some seated, others standing, some inverted and lying upside down are seen scattered on the site.

Judging from the style of carving of these monuments may be assigned to the 10th century as the carving is fairly good. Among the images of Tirthamkaras about half a dozen are those of Parasvanatha, one at least is Adinatha, and others have either no symbol or have lost them. Another

object worth-noticed in the ruins is an upper fragment (half) of a pillar 6' 5" long and 15" in diameter. The existing shaft is round but the base was probably four-sided. The top is a four-sided tenon to hold a crowning member. The portion next below is an Amalasila (or a fluted disc) having beneath it a part with four niches in four directions inset with Tirthamkaras. The lowest fragment is missing which may have borne an inscription. About two furlongs to the north of this group towards Sujwaya are two modern madhis. The bigger of the two has, as one of the pillars supporting its flat roof, an old memorial pillar of the 11th century A. D. with usual carving. This madhi shelters a large (a little bigger than life size) image of Hanuman not damaged and hence probably modern. Near to it is placed an old sculpture of Siva and Parvati. In the smaller madhi close-by is placed an old (10th century) sculpture of ten armed Kali standing. The hands on the right hold (1) a dagger, (2) a sword, (3) a human head with hair, (4) a bowl (skull), (5) a Damru and those on the left carry (6) a skull crowned mace, (7) a human head, (8) a shield, (9) a bell, (10) finger put into the mouth. The breasts are dropping down and the body shows a skeleton. She has the miniature *Bhutas as ganas*. Close to the smaller madhi is a chira or tall stone post standing on the slope of hill. It has a hole at the top and a cow and a calf carved in a panel. Opposite to this in a field below a furlong to the east is another similar chira now broken and lying prostrate. There is a superstitious legend that this latter chira has on it a figure of a wolf and its mate and that when the wolf on this post will strike the calf on the other post, a treasure will be exposed.

A furlong or more to the east of this latter chira on the slope of another hill is a modern rubble room sheltering a large old image of a six-armed goddess standing and carrying in its hands (1) a sword, (2) an unknown object, (3) a Damru, (4) an arrow, (5) a bow and (6) a shield. On one side is carved a Siva Linga after effacing of chiselling away an older figure of attendant. On the other side is the attendant still surviving. The sculpture is about six feet tall, the stone being 7½ feet above ground, the base being buried in the ground. The image is locally known as Basai-ki-Mata.

About two furlongs east of the first mentioned group of ruins on the opposite bank of Nala are the ruins of another group of temples, all Jaina. Two temples stood on a prominence side by side. The two platforms still show their lower courses *in situ*. Some deeply carved ceiling slabs are lying in the debris. There are also a few sculptures of Jaina Tirthamkaras but most of the carved debris are decorative.

A few yards further north is the site of a still another Jaina temple. A heap of debris is seen lying scattered. In this case there are quite a number of well-carved sculptures of Tirthamkaras. A Chaumukha 2' x 2' x 4' 5" is fairly well preserved. There is another sculpture now lying upside down which shows a high pedestal and a seated figure above it. The figure has preserved only its lower portion upto the waist.

Other noticeable fragment are a door-jamb, and a life size figure of Ambika (of the Jaina pantheon) half buried and without head.

Some old wells contemporary with the ruins and a Kheda or site of old habitation are shown near the first named group of temples near Malipura.

District Madasor.

Achera.—The place lies about 12 miles south-west of Mandasor on the right bank of the Seona river, about a mile to the south of the Partabgarh road. The place has nothing of archæological interest and the only object noticed is a modern gadhi. It was built by Chaman Singh Bhati Thakur of the dynasty of Jaisalmer, one of the States of Rajputana in V. S. 1716. His descendants still exist as Jagirdars. Senior most branch of Chaman-singh's family is now represented by Naharsingh (in 5th generation) who lives at Achera and is responsible for this information. The second branch is represented by another descendant who also has as his name Naharsingh and lives at Ragirkhedhi. The third branch is represented by Madhosingh at Dalanda. Chamansingh's descendants are said to have built some 24 gadhis but the list is not available.

The gadhi Achera is in a sad state of disrepair. Two bastions S. W. and S E. are practically fallen and so is the case with the mahal inside. The remaining portions are being used as quarter for the mounted guard stationed here for the watch and ward.

The Ranimahal is no more. All these buildings were enclosed in a inner wall surrounded by a moat. Behind was a line of houses probably stables or quarters along the outer-most fortifications. In the outer most line is the Dargah of Nurshah (?) a Fakir. Outside this enclosure are the temple of (Das Hanuman) now empty and a pucca platform enclosed by a dwarf compound wall with an image of Vir Hanuman.

About a furlong to the south of the foregoing chabutra in a grove stands a modest chhatri said to be that of Chamansingh, the founder of the Gadhi. It consists of a small domed chhatri on a double platform all built of black stone.

The well in the Gadhi has run dry and the Odhi (water lift) and canal from the river are now in ruins.

Achera is a decaying village and is at present held in contract by a speculator from Meerut (U. P.) The Thakur has only 500 Bighas of land in Jagir. One of the ancestors of the present Thakur fought a victorious battle with one Mirza a contractor (probably of village revenue) of Gwalior Darbar, as the Thakur possesses a sanad granted possible by the same Mirza Gulam Beg which is dated in A. H. 1241.

Bhichor.—The place is some 30 miles to the west of Singoli, by a metalled road. It has a population consisting mainly of Kumavat Thakurs who are purely agriculturists by profession. The Gadhi is quite a small one and consists of a double fortification of rubble in lime surrounded by a moat.

The entrance is through two gates. The outer gate has still preserved though in a ruined state, its old door fitted with iron spikes. The inner gate has some cut-stone work and has an image of Ganesa in a niche over

the lintel. No building has survived in the interior. In a large niche in the east wall (inside face) is placed an image of Deva Dharmaraja represented as a Raja riding on horse and locally worshipped like Khandoba in Maharashtra. The image carries a lance in his left hand and a flower in right one and has a *chhatra* and serpent above. There is a well in the south-west corner-bastion. The other bastions also are hollow inside.

The *Gadhi* is said to have been built by Thakur of Begun which is a Jagir in Udaypur State. At present the *Gadhi* is used as cattle pound.

About a hundred yards to the north of the *Gadhi* is a ruined platform of an old temple built of dressed stone but not more than 4 or 5 centuries old. The shrine is not existing but there are now collected a few fragments of old sculptures of a much earlier date, *i. e.* of the early mediæval period, among which notable is a figure of Mahishamardini.

A mile and a half further north-west on the road-side under a *palas* tree, is a broken image of Ganesa, with a line of Nagari inscription giving names of devotees. Nearby is a slab or *chira* planted upright with an inscription of sixteen lines in Nagari dated V. S. 1787, which refers to the construction of a step-well now extinct (*Vide* No. 18 of Appendix D).

Manasiagadh.—About $1\frac{1}{2}$ miles to the south of Bhichor is seen another small *gadhi* on a hill. No building is standing. Mere heaps of debris are seen from a distance. It was not examined yet at close quarters. It is locally known as *Gadh*.

Makanganj.—It is a small colony of Minas once included in the criminal tribes, which was founded as late as V. S. 1901, by one Mr. Mackintosh stationed at Neemuch (and named after him). The place lies about $2\frac{1}{2}$ miles N. E. of Bhichor and has some old ruins in its vicinity.

About $1\frac{1}{2}$ furlongs to the east of the village are two ruined shrines measuring $24'3'' \times 21'9''$ and $15'3'' \times 13''$ externally. From the style they may be dated in the 8th or even the 7th century A. D. The plan is a rectangular shrine with a projecting porch supported on two advanced pillars. There is a rectangular projection in the external face of each side wall. There is no carving except on pillars and a course on the horizontal cornice at the top. The tops of the shrines are badly damaged but possibly there were short spires on them as can be seen from the two or three fluted corner-stones such as are used in a *sikhara* lying on the site.

The horizontal course of cornice is a line of Chaitya window ornament inset with birds (ducks or swans) and geometrical squares. One medallion inset with tiger head is also lying in the debris. The shrines are set on plinths of which one at least has a rectangular platform with a *pradakshinapatha*.

The pillars are squares on plan with a decorative design of circles and ears carved in relief like those of the Solah Khambhi hall at Badoh (District Bhilsa). Over it is a square panel bearing a Kirtimukha having

pearl strings hanging from it. The Kirtimukha has over it a vase and foliage decoration. Over it is the fluted cushion and then again a vase and foliage decoration. At the top is the projecting bracket carrying the lintel.

No door-frame is preserved and the shrines are empty. Nearby are lying fragments of old bricks, which are said to have been picked up during ploughing. It means that the place is an old site and possessed more buildings in ancient times.

An image of Mahishamardini in the local Mata temple at Bhichor referred to above is said to have been removed from these ruins. Similarly a Chaumukha linga is said to have been removed from here to a village Barduni in Udaypur State, some two miles north of this place, about 50 years ago by a Brahmana and enshrined in a modern temple there. This perhaps shows that one of the old temple was sacred to Siva and the other to goddess in the form of Mahishamardini.

In a niche on the south-east shrine (in the outer face of its east wall) is an inscribed stone. The inscription is in 5th or 7th century characters in Sanskrit language and consists of 15 lines and is detailed under Epigraphy (*Vide* No. 20 of Appendix D).

The shrines are therefore very interesting links between the Gupta temples of the 5th and 6th centuries and the spired temples of early mediæval period.

The decorative carving on these temples is very much like that on the Torana pillar at Mandasor or the carvings unearthed at the Nagari excavations in the Udaypur State.

Close to the temples is an old well which according to a local tradition was built by the Pandavas. But its existing structure does not appear to be even half as old as the shrines. The original wall was perhaps contemporary with the shrine and was repaired later on. The head of a stone idol is built up in the wall of the well.

Jat.—The place is situated about 20 miles to the west of Ratangarh. It was visited by my assistant some years back and the present visit was with a view to see its fort. The fort of Jat stands on a hillock of laterite but has nothing of interest historically or architecturally except that the shape of the bastions being like a vase at the base is noteworthy.

The only object of interest noted here is a copper plate grant of V. S. 1705, in the possession of a 55 years old Gujar Gaud Brahmana named Prabhulal who still enjoys the land in *Muafi*. The grant was made by Raja Rajsinghji of Begun whose forefathers, it is said, have built the forts at Ratangarh, Jat, Bhichor and Lasur. The present Jagirdar is Thakur Anupsinghji.

Morvana.—It is a small village about 15 miles north of Neemuch on the road to Ratangarh. It was visited once before and an interesting head of a god was recovered from here. The place was therefore re-examined this year but yielded nothing of particular interest except the following:—

- (1) Fragments of an image of Surya in a collection on the road side,
- (2) a memorial pillar on a chhatra near Mata temple just outside the north

of village, (3) a collection of broken sculptures worshipped as Mata among which are a Mahishamardini, a figure of Chhaya (Surya's wife), pieces of carved door frame, etc., (4) ruins of an old temple and (5) a group of *sati*-stones of the 15th to 18th centuries with crude and illegible inscriptions. None of these are of more than ordinary interest.

Ratangarh.—It is a small town with a strong hill fort about 35 miles by road to the north-east of Neemuch. The fort does not appear to be older than the 17th century. It is of fairly large dimensions and commands a picturesque situation. It is built mostly of rubble stone in mud, with a sparing use of bricks and plaster. The masonry in some parts is of a diaper pattern. Some of the buildings in the fort are:—(1) Balaji-ka-burj with a gate of a multifoil arch, and a *sati* stone near it, (2) a well, (3) a mosque, (4) Kacheri in ruins, (5) a temple of Ramji (which looks to be a modern shrine with a five panel *mandapa* on a high plinth with a flight of steps to get up and a small rubble compound in front. A piece of an inscribed *sati* pillar dated V. S. 1608 (?) is lying in the compound. The sculpture on the *sati* pillar shows armed horsemen and a woman with folded hands in front now bedaubed with *sindur*. The temple which is used for worship, is in fair condition), (6) two oblong reservoirs for storage of water built in *juxta* position to one another (the bigger one measures 103' × 29' and the smaller 81'6" × 30' the depth being over 24'. These are made of brick in lime and preserved fairly), (7) another cistern of masonry plastered over called *chopda* almost square on plan and (8) six pucca granaries or under-ground cellars with a round opening probably closed with stone covers for storage of grain. They are situated in an open enclosure and are still intact.

The ravine coming down from Goraji's shrine on the north-side of the fort is dammed near below the N. W. corner. A little above is the *char-burj* which is a miniature *gadhi* so called on account of the four bastions one at each corner.

There is a *khidki* or a small gate in the south fort-wall with a by-path to get down to the village. On the east the main fortification-wall is protected by two more enclosure walls and a moat. There is another *khidki* in the outer-most defence enclosure.

The main fort-wall is about 10 to 12 feet wide. Behind the battlements is a broad passage about 8 feet wide all round. There are stairs and *rapats* (masonry slopes) to get to this passage from ground inside, most of them being intact. The slopes were evidently provided for taking the cannon (?) upto the battlements.

Thakurai.—It is a small village about 15 miles, west of Singoli by road. Less than quarter of a mile to the west of the village stand the ruins of a Siva (?) temple of about the 10th century A. D. The temple faced roughly to the N. E. It stood on a high plinth which consisted of a number of horizontal mouldings. It seems to have consisted of a shrine-room with a porch which has now disappeared completely. The walls of the shrine are standing partially. The doorway has the right

jamb and sill *in situ*. The other jamb is lying in the debris. The lower panel on the standing jamb has a *gana* holding a *trisula* (trident) which would show that the temple was sacred to Siva. The lintel which would have decided the matter clearly, is missing. The outer face of the shrine has survived only on the proper right wall. It shows two niches one of which shelters an image of Ganesa and the other that of Siva transfixing the Gaja (demon).

On one end of the sill is carved Ganesa and on the other (right) is Kubera. In the centre is the conventional lotus plant, in between are two Kirtimukhas.

In the carved stones lying on the site can be seen an image of Balarama (four armed) with a canopy of five heads of snake. The door jambs are decorated with small panels, containing Hindu gods Vishnu, Siva etc.

At the back of the temple is a *sati* stone lying prostrate bearing the images of the couple in a sunken panel and an inscription with a damaged date. Another *sati* stone with an inscription of V. S. 1757 is standing on a platform on the N. W. of the shrine.

A small *gadhi* or rather a Thakur's house stood closely on a Tila or hillock but it has disappeared leaving only its gate, with a cutstone door frame and a multifoil mehrab.

District Narwar.

Budera.—It is a small village about four miles to south-east of Gudar, a Jagir village in Pichhore Pargana. In the limits of this village and close to the north-east end of the Jhaloni tank, stands on a hillock, a rough dressed pillar 18 feet high above ground and $15'' \times 11\frac{1}{2}''$ in section. It bears a crudely engraved inscription dated V. S. 1351 and refers to Chanderi and its Bundela rulers. As the inscription is not fully legible the exact purpose of the erection of the pillar is not clear.

Gudar.—It is a village owned in Jagir by Bundela Thakurs, descendants of the Bundela Rajas of Chanderi. The village stands on the slope of a hill about four miles to the south of Khaniadhana, the capital of a small State of the same name and can be reached from Pichhore or from Basai Railway Station direct, distance being 20 miles by both the routes. The present habitation is not very old as a deserted site about a mile to the south is said to be the original site of Gudar. Gudar is shown as Gudari in the State Gazetteer map.

But the area immediately below this modern village and to its north is studded with antiquities of the 10-12th centuries both Hindu and Jaina. On the top of the hill overlooking the village are seen the remnants of fortifications which mark the limits of a small fort or *gadhi* but no other ruins of any kind are seen there except a temple of a goddess who is worshipped once a year. Between the top of the hill and the village but nearer to the latter is a gateway with a multifoil arch built of brick and fragments of wallings. It is said to be another *gadhi* built by the ancestors of the Thakurs of Gudar which they abandoned

About a few yards below this ruined *gadhi* or near the upper skirts of the village stands a comparatively modern Jaina temple which being whitewashed is prominently visible from a distance. The building is of a modern type built of brick and stone in mud and plastered over with lime, though a few pillars and other stones of 12th century temples are built up in its verandah. According to the inscription near its entrance this temple was built in V. S. 1812, but some of the idols enshrined are considerably older, as three of them bear on their pedestals inscriptions dated V. S. 1391. These are all seated Jainas of brass except two, which are of stone.

In the village itself the only object of some antiquarian interest is a number of fragments of old sculptures collected in a modern *madhi* or hut near the Jagirdar's house and worshipped as Mata (goddess). Among the carvings the more prominent are (1) a door jamb, (2) Vishnu and Lakshmi on Garuda, (3) a mother with a child, (4) Siva with Parvati, (5-10) Ganesa, (11-13) Vishnus, (14) a Siva Linga, (15) Garuda and (16) a garland bearer.

Other relics lying in the area in front (east) of the village are as under :—

On the lower outskirts of the village is a group of three small shrines one of which faces to the east, other to the west while the third is in quite a ruined condition. In the shrine facing the east and measuring $8\frac{1}{2}' \times 5\frac{3}{4}'$ externally are stored a few old sculptures namely, (1) Vamana incarnation of Vishnu, (2) Brahma and (3) Lakshmi. The sculptures are probably not the original belongings of this temple as it seems to be *Saiva* one from the image of Ganesa in the centre of the dedicatory block on the lintel of the door-way. The shrine facing the west is $5\frac{3}{4}' \times 8'$ externally. The door frame is similar to that of the foregoing shrine. Inside is a Siva linga. There are small porches in front of each shrine and the walls are made of single slabs placed on edge. The third shrine of this group has left more traces. The fragments of sculptures lying here are (1) Brahma and Brahmani, (2-3) Ganesa, (4) Lakshmi standing, (5) Brahma seated and (6) a Siva linga. The lintel of a door-frame lying on the site has Siva in the centre and shows that the temple was sacred to that god. A large ceiling slab lying closely with a lotus flower carved on the underside is measuring $7\frac{3}{4}' \times 6\frac{3}{4}'$ and belongs probably to it.

About four furlongs away to the north-east of this group on the outskirts of rice fields stands the image of a goddess which is $7\frac{1}{2}'$ high and is locally known as that of Anjani, the mother of Hanuman probably owing to the presence of a modern idol of Hanuman in its close proximity.

About two furlongs to the north of the group of Siva temples described above and a furlong from the village almost opposite to the modern Jaina temple, stand in a field three big images of Jaina Tirthankaras facing almost to the west, two smaller ones (each $6\frac{1}{2}'$ high) flanking the central bigger sculpture ($9'$ high). One of the side sculptures has a symbol of an antelope on its pedestal and the other has a fish. The bigger central sculpture had its feet and pedestal concealed in the ground, which when cleared

of V. S. 1476 (*Vide* No. 27 of Appendix D). Half a mile further from the site, on the way to Jhaloni, are two *sati* stones with inscriptions dated V. S. 1527 and V. S. 14 (8) 5 respectively.

Sesai.—The place was visited for a second time, and the under-mentioned new information was added to the previous notes.

About a hundred feet to the west of the larger Jaina temple is a memorial pillar bearing an inscription in two pieces. The pillar is 5' high above ground, 1' 8" broad and 8" thick and faces east. It has three panels of sculptures. The central panel is surrounded with a frame of which the upper and lower borders together bear an interesting inscription which on palaeographical grounds may be assigned to 6-7th century A. D. (*Vide* No. 37 of Appendix D). The inscription records the voluntary self-cremation of a sorrowing mother after her sons had met heroes' death on battle field. This makes it a memorial of more than usual interest. Two more inscribed *sati* pillars stand close to this memorial pillar.

A small old shrine of Siva was noticed this year a hundred yards S. E. of the temples, standing near the above memorial stone, which were already known. The new shrine is in ruins and has nothing of particular interest.

By the side of the cart-track passing by the south wall of the *sarai* is an old but ruined step-well now past repairs. Close to this is lying a damaged sculpture of Jina seated. It has no distinctive symbol or *Lanchhana* but on the pedestal lions are carved as usual.

Tongra.—A village some eight miles to the S. W. of Shivpuri in this district was visited this year to compare the notes on monuments listed and described in last year's report. Here no more monuments came to light during the present visit.

District Shajapur.

Agar.—Is a pretty town 41 miles by road north of Ujjain and was once a British Cantonment. The town is picturesquely situated between two tanks and surrounded by a city wall too but is destitute of any remains of archaeological interest. The only object of some interest is the temple of Sri Baijnath Mahadeva which though built in modern times contains in its womb remains of an older temple. Some carved stones too are built up here and there among which is an old sculpture of Siva and Parvati seated on Nandi which probably belonged to the original temple of the 11th or 12th century A. D. The present temple consists of a shrine-room and a *sabhamandapa* in front facing west, the whole being set on a high plinth accessible by a flight of spacious steps. The *sabhamandapa* measuring 29' 3" by 27' 1" has five lines of four pillars, each of which supports the roof. The shrine-room is crowned with a high spire and the *sabhamandapa* with two adjacent domes. The whole monument is 64' 9" long east and west and 29' 3" broad north and south.

The *linga* in the shrine appears to be an old one but the *Salunka* or *Jaladhari* is covered with a brass sheet as also the half moon-stone in front of the sill of the shrine-door.

The temple in its present form was built in the August of 1882 by the order of Col. Martin, Officer Commanding, Agar cantonment, as recorded in an inscription painted in plaster and still preserved.

A stream called Banganga flows closeby and Col. Martin has put six low dams on it to hold water for visitors at the annual *mela*.

There is a small tank at the back of the temple called Kamal Kund on account of red lotuses which grow in it. There is also a small cistern near the N. W. corner of the temple called Gau Kund.

It is said that the Col.'s interest in the temple was roused by his wife who revered the Deity as her Benefactor. The legend runs that Col. Martin was on active service in the 2nd Afghan War. His family was behind in the cantonment. It so happened that for a long time Mrs. Martin had no news of her husband and naturally became very anxious about his safety. About that very time, the annual *mela* came off, which is being held at this temple every year in the bright half of Chaitra (March-April). As the Col.'s wife saw crowds of people going to the temple for *darsan* she enquired what the matter was. She was told that the people gathered to worship God *Siva*, who fulfils the wishes of his earnest devotees. With a heavy and impatient heart she went to the *pujari* and asked if his deity would grant her wishes. The *pujari* informed her that if her prayers were earnest and sincere, the lord would certainly bless her. She therefore avowed that if she received the news of the Col.'s safety or he returned safe she would have the god's temple built on a large scale, and lo ! to her surprise she received the Col.'s letter by the next Mail and he himself returned safely after due time. In fulfilment of her vow this temple was built in its present form.

The surroundings of the temple are very charming. The inside of the shrine is adorned with mural paintings depicting scenes from the *Siva purana* which are worthy of appreciation both for the happy choice of subjects and their proper execution. The subjects are (1) Two armed Siva sitting alone on the peaks of Kailasa, (2) Siva coming as a young ascetic to Parvati practising penance accompanied by her maid (Cf. *Kumarasambhava*) labelled "Parvati Prema Pariksha" or the test of Parvati's love, (3) Siva protecting Markandeya against Yama, (4) Parvati propitiating Siva, (5) Ganga Avatarana or the descent of the Ganges, (6) Madana Dahana or the cremation of the cupid, (7) Marriage of Siva and Parvati and (8) Siva carrying the corpse of Parvati on his shoulders or the sorrow of Siva.

There is a number of *samadhis* in the form of Chhatris or *otalas* or open platforms only.

A *matha* for the *pujari* to live in, has also been built closeby, but is incomplete as the donor, the Col. was transferred before its completion and his successor took no notice of it. The *pujari* who carried on the worship of the temple is Gosain of the Puri lineage, as is clear from his name Chandrapuri. These Gosains generally lead a married life but the heirship of right to worship is handed down from *guru* to *chela* or from

teacher to pupil and not to a born heir. The present *pujari* Kanchanapuri is the 3rd in line from Mangalapuri in whose time the temple was repaired, and enjoys a cash *muaji* from the State.

The following modern temples stand in the close vicinity of this great temple: (1) Varaha temple facing east in which is enshrined a well-preserved old sculpture of Varaha (man-shaped) lifting the goddess of earth.

- (2) Ganesa temple facing west.
- (3) Kala Bhairava to the north-east.
- (4) Hanuman to south-east, and
- (5) Mangalanath to south.

Shajapur.—The headquarters of the district of the same name, is a small town in Malwa said to have been founded by the order of and named after the Emperor Shahjahan who happened to stay here on his way to Deccan about 1640 A. D. It lies on the Agra Bombay trunk road and is about 200 miles south of Gwalior.

The place has the following remains of old buildings most of which dated from the Moghul Emperors.

(1) *Shahibagh*.—the garden is now in ruins, but still possesses vestiges of decorations, cisterns, water shades, fountains, etc. such as were used in Moghul gardens. The present owners are Syad Abdul Wahid who is remarkably energetic for his years, and his son Abdul Sattar.

(2) *Badshahi pul* or bridge.—It is a dam some fifteen feet in thickness now wearing away on the river Chilhad (old name Sagarmati).

(3) *Shahimahal*.—Close to the bridge are to be seen ruins of a building called Shahimahal, a portion of which is now covered with a tin shed and used as a temple. Nearby is a small shrine of Hanuman on a small platform.

(4) *Jama Masjid*.—The mosque appears to have been built in Aurangzeb's time, and is 5 bays wide and 2 bays deep. It is devoid of any architectural pretensions, as all the works of the time of this severely Puritan Emperor. It has three domes on the roof and two minarets in the back corners. The building is set on a high plinth and has a suitable courtyard in front surrounded by a compound wall with a doorway approached by a flight of steps from the outside. It has a Persian inscription in two lines of verse which names the builder as Hyder Ali and architect (?) as Mir Kala and gives the date as A. H. 1088, on Abjad system which is also engraved in ciphers and reads 1088.

The chief monument in the town, however, is a small fort on the left bank of the river Sagarmati. The fort wall is fairly well preserved. Ancient buildings in it have either been replaced with modern buildings or have been so repaired as to look quite modern for use as local state offices, all of which are housed in the fort. The buildings called mahals now used for the office and the residence of the Suba are said to have been built by Maharani Tara Bai Sahiba, one of the consorts of Maharaja Daulat Rao Scindia of Gwalior.

Shujalpur.—Is a town with mandi near the Shujalpur Railway Station on the Ujjain-Bhopal line whence it is a mile away. The town is also connected with Agra Bombay road by branch road of 20 miles. It is nearly 60 miles to the east of Shajapur.

The place has a history of 500 years at its back and is well known in the history of Malwa. Though it possesses no ruins of antiquarian interest, it has close to it a monument of first rate historical importance so far as the ruling house of Gwalior is concerned, namely, the Chhatri of Maharaja Ranoji Rao Scindia, the founder of the Gwalior house. The Chhatri has already been noticed in the past year and was visited this time again. A note suggesting some improvements in the building and its premises has been drawn up and submitted to Home Member Sahib for approval and necessary action.

But Shujalpur was visited this year in response of a report received from the Judicial and Education Departments about underground building exposed accidentally during an excavation for building purposes and the site was examined in the presence of the Inspector of Schools and the Judicial and Police Officers.

The present school building is a structure built on the site of a fort or *gadhi* of the Muhammadan period. The *gadhi* is surrounded by a Nala which serves as a moat. The present diggings for an extension of school buildings have exposed a passage with a flight of steps leading down in a northerly direction between two walls and a vaulted ceiling all of brick in mud pointed with lime. As usual the exposed structure was suspected by people to be an underground cellar for hiding a treasure or to be some interesting piece of architecture and the diggings were suspended pending report of the Archæological Department. Popular suspicions were proved to be unfounded. So far as I could surmise it is a secret passage for escape in times of emergency as so many forts have been found to provide such passages or else it may be a passage to reach a *baodi* (step-well) situated in one of the bastions in the north wall or rather outside the north wall of the fort, or even to a *ghat* on the Nala. It appears to have been closed with blocks of stone in lime at its either end. In any case the structure exposed proved to be of no archæological or architectural interest.

Some people still suspect or hope to find treasure concealed there, as they say, by the Pendharis in whose strong-hold the place was for some time. I am unable to express any opinion as to the possibility or otherwise of such a contingency. At any rate the Archæological Department is in no way concerned in hunting hidden treasures for their money value.

Umarkot.—Is a small village about 10 miles, north of Susner and a mile and a half away from the Agar Susner road. The place was visited to examine a *chhatri* reported by the local Revenue Officers to be an old one and in a precarious condition. The *chhatri* however turned to be a comparatively modern structure devoid of architectural or historical interest.

Here there is a small fort which stands picturesquely on the right bank of the Nala which bounds it on the north. The bank here is a steep cut-rock on which the north wall of the fort is or rather was built. There are now no buildings worth the name left in the fort.

The fort is said to have been built by Umar Khan and Sitar Khan, two enterprising brothers from Gazni and named Umarmkot after them. But curiously enough, the fort has no mosque, tomb, or any other vestige of Islam which fact contradicts the above tradition. On the other hand, there are two temples one of Siva and the other of Devadharmaraja, two *Tulsi vrindavanas* and a Hindu *chhatri*. Hence the other tradition seems more possible according to which the fort was built by a Brahmana named Girmaji Rao. He built the buildings on the fort and the temple of Devadharmaraja and garden etc. The *chhatri* is said to commemorate the founder of the fort.

At present the west and south walls are standing. The west wall has four bastions and had *khidki* gates in two bastions while the main gate is in the east wall.

Other objects noted here are an inscribed *chira* (post) in front of Nara Mandir. It stands against the abutment of the proper right wall of the *Sabhamandapa* of the temple. In front of it is a *Tulsi vrindavana*. The temple is a modern one of brick and lime and is said to have been built in the reign of Maharaja Daulat Rao Scindia by a Bania of Metwal caste.

District Tonwarghar.

Amladha.—Is a village one mile N. E. of Mitaoli. The ruins noticed here are mostly shrines of Siva. But one of the shrines facing west, has a figure of Vishnu on the central block of its door frame. The only shrine which is better preserved measures 5' x 5'9" internally and 7'10" x 9" externally. The walls are faced with single slabs. The outer face of each wall has two niches inset with figures of gods and goddesses and flanked by figures of *dikpalas* or guardians of quarters, as under:—

North (1) Parvati standing and (2) Siva seated, in niches. Varuna, Vayu and Kubera flank the above. East, (1) Surya seated and (2) Kartikeya standing, in niches, flanked by Isha, Sadhu and Agni. South, (1) Rudra (?) and (2) Ganesa both standing, in niches, flanked by Indra, Yama and Nairiti. The shrine is on a plinth 7 feet high above the ground. The carved facing of the plinth has now disappeared exposing the inner core.

A damaged sculpture of Hanuman and a fragment of another besmeared with red lead exist close by to the east of the shrine.

Nearby to the north of the above shrine are the ruins of another bigger temple of Siva (?). Only the lower portion of the platform with the upper railing of the *Sabhamandapa* is all that exist. There is also a Siva *linga* and the lintel of a door-frame on the platform. As the structure is half buried in earth and covered over with fodder, a minute examination was not possible. The platform roughly measures 32' x 24.'

Two unfinished sculptures, one entire and the other only lower half fragment, of Saptamatrikas have recently been unearthed in the bed of an old tank close to the east of the aforesaid ruins.

Further east are two *sati* stones set up back to back. The one facing west has an inscription now too much worn. The carving on the post is also shallow and crude.

Ardoni.—Is a good village 2 miles to the north of Padhavli and seems to be old one. On my way through the village I saw a round well built of large dressed stone blocks, now silted up. It has a massive beam laid across it and a channel cut in stone slab with a crocodile or lion (?) spout at one end. The platform of the well which was also round is no longer extant with the exception of a few stones which carry the beam and the spout.

A little further towards the village stand the remains of an old shrine which consists of a cell and a porch in front. In the north-side wall is an image of Ganesa now facing inside. But originally the sculpture faced outside. The inner side of the wall was plain. The porch is reconstructed. The shrine room and the porch measure about 8' × 3' respectively.

Closeby is a worn-out Kamal-Surya pedestal and ruined old carvings. The image of Hanuman near it appears modern. Further north along the track to the left in a field stand two *sati* stones, one of which has an inscription dated V. S. 1442.

Batesvar Valley.—About a mile S. W. of Padhavli, in the band of hills lie scattered ruins of numerous temples and habitation. The place is known as Batesvar on account of a temple of Siva locally called Batesvar Mahadev. The place appears to have been a religious centre studded with numerous temples in the days when Padhavli was flourishing. Padhavli possesses numerous remnants of both Hindu and Jaina shrines and sculptures. These have been already described in previous Reports. The place was visited again this year with an object of selecting some loose sculptures for the Museum. During this quest were further noticed (1) remains of an old tank with sculptures stuck up in the wall, (2) two old wells, (3) a pair of Naga sculptures and (4) a memorial pillar lying broken in three pieces with usual sculptures. One of the above wells had a three storeyed passage now ruined, while the other had placed beside it a monolithic stone trough measuring 7' 8" × 3' 4" × 1' 7".

Bharaoli.—Is a small village lying on the slope of the hill or almost on the back of Batesvar valley. This village is reached by cart track two miles in length or a mile by footpath direct. Being in the close vicinity of Padhavli the place possesses some ruins.

One of these is an entire temple of Siva with its *sikhara* and *Sabhamandapa*, but is at present enveloped in *kuchcha* houses raised by Pujaris. It stands in the village and regular worship is carried on.

Along the way to the temple lie on a *chabutra* some broken images both Hindu and Jaina, among which are Kubera and Yaksha.

Below the village towards the east lie good many *sati* stones, some of which are dated in V. S. 1439, 1539, 1594, 1675, while many have no inscription at all. Further south is an old well.

Bhensoda.—Is a village between two or three miles to the north-east of Padbavli. An irrigation canal passes within a quarter of a mile to the north. On the north-west out-skirts of the village within a hundred yards from it stand the ruins of a Siva temple of about the 10th century A. D. The temple faces east. What now remains is the shrine-room deprived of the *sikhara* and partially of the outer facing of the walls. The surviving facing shows the usual sculpture of the guardians of the quarters and other gods of Hindu pantheon all facing the west. Notable among these are the two sculptures in niches in the central portion of the back. In the upper central niche is an image of standing Surya with upraised hands holding lotuses. In the lower niche are Siva and Parvati standing side by side. The door-frame of the shrine has been lost with the exception of the sill. A half part of the door lintel from the debris shows Siva in the centre and Brahma at one end. The Siva *linga* which is worshipped inside appears to be original. The shrine stood on a high plinth which has its inner core completely exposed having lost the outer facing.

In the central niche on the south wall (outer face) of the shrine in the central course is a sculpture of Hari Hara.

A mass of carved stones, lintels, brackets, pedestals of pillars lying on the site prove the existence of a fairly large *Sabhamandapa*. A major fragment of a large *amalasila* now kept upright in the form of an arch, a figure of seated Ganesa, a Nandi and that of a standing Nairiti may be particularly noticed. There were three horizontal courses of niches in the outer decoration of walls the uppermost of which has mostly disappeared. The ceiling slab has a lotus on its under side.

No inscription was found in the debris. A big *pipal* tree growing at the site is responsible for this havoc.

Ruins of another smaller temple lie to the south of the village along the cart-track. The ruins are too poor to need description in as much as a single worn-out sculpture of Mahishamardini is lying near it.

Nurabad.—Is a small village on the Agra-Bombay road 15 miles north of Gwalior on the Sank river. It is known for its *sarai* and the bridge on the river on the banks of which the village is situated. Both are examples of late Moghul architecture and were built during the reign of Aurangzeb. These have already been examined and the object of this visit was a Persian inscription said to have been lying loose in a modern mosque outside the *sarai*.

The inscription under reference refers to the construction of a mosque, which is said to have existed once in the centre of the *sarai* as usual and was contemporary with the same. The inscription is detailed in the Appendix D. (*Vide* No. 39). It is at present built up in the eastern face of the prayer hall of a new mosque, which stands at the N. W.

corner of the *sarai*. The mosque is used for prayers and is said to be about 50 years old.

Padhavli.—Lies about 4 miles to the west of Rithora Railway Station. The place is strewn over with numerous ruins already known. The place was visited this year in connection with the direction of the conservation work of one of the monuments in progress.

This year two old memorial stones were exposed in an excavation. Both are inscribed and referable to the Gupta period and have usual carved panels. One of them is inscribed in Gupta characters and the other has inscribed on it some mysterious big letter of Sal characters (?) which has still baffled decipherment.

Rithora.—Is a big village and a station on G. L. Railway. The village has few old memorial pillars. These memorial pillars which are about 14 centuries old have already been noticed. This year an inscription hitherto unnoticed was found on one of these pillars. The inscription is analysed under Epigraphy (*Vide* No. 41, Appendix No. D).

VIII Epigraphy.

Forty-three inscriptions ranging in date from the 5th to the 19th century A. D. were noticed and copied during the year of report. Of these twelve are in Sanskrit, twenty-five in Hindi, one in Marathi, while four are in Persian and one is illegible.

Of the inscriptions copied two are most important and are already published. They are (1) a Gupta inscription from a well at Mandsaur, circa A. D. 437-38 (*Vide* Dr. Fleet's *Gupta Inscriptions* pp. 150 plate XXII) and (2) Sun temple inscription of Mihirakula, from Gwalior Fort circa 5th Century A. D. (*Ibid* pp. 161 plate XXIII B). The stone of the former is in the possession of Miss B. Filose of Gwalior and that of the latter is in the Indian Museum, Calcutta. As these were among the most interesting records of the ancient history of Central India, they were copied and the copies were preserved in record of estampages.

The Sanskrit inscription on a memorial pillar from Sesai (No. 37) in late Gupta characters of about 6th or 7th century stands next in importance. It records the voluntary cremation of a bereaved mother with her sons who were killed in a battle. There have been in ancient India innumerable cases of wives burning themselves along with their husbands. But this case of a mother burning herself with her dead sons is quite unique and this makes the inscription of special interest.

The next important inscription comes from Makanganj (No. 20). It is inscribed in old Nagari characters of the 7-8th century but being very badly damaged is all but completely lost. The inscribed surface has peeled off and only a few letters here and there can be deciphered. There are the names of Dutta Simha and his son Gopa Simha who were members of either the then ruling dynasty or of the donor's family.

The rest of the inscriptions come from *sati* stones, memorial pillars and modern temples, etc. Among these may be mentioned one from Chanderi (No. 10) which gives a genealogy of the Bundela kings of Chanderi, beginning from the founder and ending with Manasingh, the son of Durjansingh. Two of the *sati* records mention wrong names of rulers, *i. e.*, Gahawarkhan for Dilawarkhan and Mahmud Ghizni for Mahmud Khilji of Mandu.

The Persian inscriptions refer to the construction of mosques and stepwells and mention Mahmud Shah Khilji of Mandu, Sultan Ibrahim Lodi and Emperor Aurangzeb of Delhi.

The detailed analysis of the inscriptions is set forth in the Appendix D.

IX Numismatics.

Five gold, sixty-three silver, 242 copper or 310 coins in all were examined during the year of report. They range in date from the 11th to the 18th century A. D. Of these, five gold coins were received as present from the Government of H. E. H. the Nizam of Deccan, while the remaining silver and copper coins were come as treasure-trove finds from three different places in the State, *viz.* Chanderi (District Esagarh), Baradiya Gujar (District Mandasor) and Dawatpur (District Shajapur).

The gold coins represent the Yadava dynasty of Devagiri of the 12th century A. D. and the second dynasty of Vijayanagar of the 13th century A. D. Of the 63 silver coins, 22 were Gadhiya pieces of the Indo-Sassanian class of a crude type and the remaining belonged to the Moghul Emperors of Delhi. These Muhammadan coins relate to Aurangzeb, Farrukh Siyar, Muhammad Shah and Shah Alam II and represent Etawah, Agra, Gwalior, Delhi, Kura, Surat and Murshidabad mints.

The copper coins were also of the Gadhiya variety representing a degenerated copy of the Indo-Sassanian coinage, bearing as it does on the obverse a crude imitation of king's bust and on the reverse lines and dots suggesting the Sassanian fire altar; the hoard may roughly be assigned to the 11th century A. D.

As all these types of coinage are already in stock, only the five gold coins received as present were retained for the Museum of Archæology. For detailed analysis see Appendix No. E.

X Museum.

Three stone inscriptions, two impressions of inscriptions, one terra cotta image, three stone sculptures, three stone heads and one limb, three old miniature paintings, one photographic chart and five gold coins or twenty-two antiquities in all were added to the Museum in the year of report. All the acquisitions except the last item come from within the State. The photographic chart giving views of the early residence of Scindia Patils at Jamgaon, District Ahmadnagar in the Deccan was secured through the good offices of Shrimant Khase Sahib Pawar, Home Member, Gwalior Government. Five gold coins were received as present from the Government of H. E. H. the Nizam of Hyderabad Deccan, to whom our cordial thanks are due.

The importance and popularity of the Gwalior Archæological Museum has been established now and hardly any visitor to Gwalior leaves this place without seeing this institution. The above assertion is borne out by the visitor's book maintained in the Museum. Seven hundred and sixty Indians and one hundred eighty-six foreigners have recorded their names and remarks of appreciation in the above-mentioned visit-book, although the actual number of visitors was far greater than the figures quoted above because some of them either do not choose to sign or leave the task to their Secretary when they visit in parties. The Indian visitors represent almost all provinces of India and Ceylon while the foreigners include people from different parts of the globe, most of them being tourists from the United Kingdom, the United States of America, Germany, Switzerland, Russia and China. The following are some of the distinguished visitors who visited the Museum in the year of report:—

H. H. the Maharaja of Bhavanagar.

H. H. the Nawab of Cambay.

H. H. the Raja and Rani of Jasdan with their parties, Sir Stanley Jackson; Sir Frank and Lady Noyce the President, and Nawab A. F. M. Abdul Ali the Secretary, and Members of the Indian Historical Records Commission with Sir Jadunath Sarkar, G. S. Sardesai, Principal Rawlinson, Dr. Aiyangar and Sardar Kibe; Sir B. L. Mitra, the Law Member of the Government of India and Lady Mitra; Sir Prabha Shankar Pattani, President of the Council of Regency, Bhavnagar; Mr. and Mrs. Yazdani of Hyderabad Archæological Department; Pt. Varajlal Mayashankar Acharya of Rajkot; Pt. A. Nilkhantha Shastri, Professor of History and Archæology, Madras University; Mr. Diskalkar, Curator, Muttra Museum; Mr. Pal Chaudhry, M. L. C.; Mr. H. G. Waterfield, Inspector General of Police, Gwalior and Mr. F. Pearce, Principal of the Sardars' School, Gwalior Fort.

Besides the above, the members of the Society of History and Economics, Gujrat College, Ahmadabad and Parsi Scouting Society of Bombay, Principal and staff of the Balwant College, Agra and a party of Indian tourists from Calcutta visited the institution.

The Malwa Division of the State is a very important part of Scindia's territories and besides has a history of its own of no less antiquity or interest than that of any other province. Its capital Ujjain, was a most important religious, cultural and commercial centre in ancient India and is one of the most venerable places of pilgrimage in modern India. Here crowds of pilgrims flock every year from far and near. Among the visitors are many scholars and lovers of antiquity as well. This latter class, however, felt much disappointed not to find much of antiquarian interest in the modern city. In order to remove this long-felt want, the establishment of a Museum of Archæology at Ujjain had been the object of the Department, subject to approval of the Government. The original scheme is still pending final sanction. But with the approval of the Home Member, a small beginning has been made in this direction in the year,

meeting the expenditure from the existing grant for Museum. Forty-two sculptures have been collected so far from different quarters of the city proper and exhibited in a part of the spacious verandah of Dharmashala of the great Mahakal temple, the only place which attracts all the visitors to Ujjain. It is hoped to develop this collection into a decent Museum in due course if funds permit. The antiquities collected for both the Museums are set forth in Appendices F (1) and F (2).

XI. Important Events of the Year.

(a) At-Home.

It will be seen from the Annual Administration Reports of the previous years that the Department holds an At-Home, generally at the Archæological Museum, periodically with a view to attract and bring the general public in touch with the activities of this Department, to rouse their interest in matters of Archæology and History and to secure their sympathy and co-operation.

Such a function took place in the year of report on the occasion of the Session of the Indian Historical Records Commission held at Gwalior in December 1929. The principal feature of this year's gathering was that our beloved young Maharaja H. H. Jiwaji Rao Scindia personally met the members of the Indian Historical Records Commission along with the Resident, the Sardars, Members of the Council, Officers and gentry of the State in an At-Home at the Archæological Museum. The guests were taken round the Museum, the arrangement of which they greatly appreciated. Afterwards light refreshments were served to the accompaniment of Music both Indian and European. The At-Home was attended by the party of school-boys from England who happened to be at Gwalior on that day. On the whole the function was very picturesque and successful.

(b) Indian Historical Records Exhibition.

The Indian Historical Records Commission which was invited by the Gwalior Government, to hold its annual session this year at Gwalior, held an exhibition also, as usual, at Gwalior. Besides other work in connection with the Commission's activities here, that of organising the exhibition was specially entrusted to this Department by the local Committee. The exhibition had two main sections. One consisted of exhibits from British India which were brought and arranged by the authorities of Indian Historical Records Commission and the other section represented mostly Indian India, *i. e.*, Gwalior, Hyderabad, Baroda, Indore, Dhar, Rutlam and other States. The work of the latter section of the exhibition was specially carried out by this Department and thanks to the co-operation of the authorities of Indian Historical Records Commission, the Members of the Council of Regency, the Sardars, Officers, and the gentry of the State, that the Department could acquit itself successfully. The exhibits of the various kinds, old arms, fresco paintings, miniature paintings, Firmans, Sanads, State treaties and Records, copper plates and stone inscriptions, manuscripts, coins and other curio of historical nature were kept in view,

all properly arranged and duly labelled for the guidance of visitors. The old arms of the Military Department of the State were exhibited most artistically and tastefully. The exhibits were over fifteen hundred in number, of which 1,000 came purely from within the State and ranged in date from B. C. 150 to the very close of the 19th century. All the exhibits from far and wide were received, taken care of and returned carefully to their owners without the least loss or damage.

The exhibition was opened by H. H. the Maharaja George Jiwaji Rao Sahib Scindia, Alijah Bahadur of Gwalior, and was visited by the Senior and Junior Maharanis, H. E. the Commander-in-chief in India, The Resident, the Members of the Council of Regency, the distinguished guests, the Sardars, Officers, and the public at large of the State. Special arrangements were made for the pardah ladies. The collection of Moghul and Rajput paintings from British India was very remarkable and was highly appreciated by visitors. The section of the State arms was also specially talked of. Further details of the exhibition will be found in the report of the Indian Historical Records Commission.

(c) Distinguished Visitors to the Monuments.

Leaving aside the Archæological Museum and the other monuments at Gwalior proper, some of the important groups of Archæological Monuments in the districts are also steadily gaining in popularity and attracting visitors. The following names are taken from the visitor's book maintained at the following places :—

(1) *Bagh Caves*.—Rao Bahadur S. M. Bapna, Prime Minister of Indore; Sir Hukumchand of Indore; Dr. S. R. Oke of Dewas; Maharaja Bharat Singh of Multan and General G. R. Rajwade, the Army Member; Dr. Antia, Chief Medical Officer; Mr. M. S. Bhagwat, Revenue Secretary; Mr. M. V. Lele retired Engineer, all of Gwalior Government.

(2) *Bhilsa*.—G. S. Sardesai, Historian, Poona; Prof. C. V. Joshi, Huzur Daftardar, Baroda; Dr. S. R. Oke of Dewas; Prof. Qanungo of Dacca University and Behore Rajendrasingh, M. R. A. S., M. L. C. (C. P.).

XII. Photographs and Drawings.

One hundred and forty-six Photographs were taken during the year of report. Besides the usual set of photo prints required for the annual record and the Darbar Album, over 200 prints from the record-negatives were prepared for departmental publications and for illustrating the works of different authors and institutions who applied for them. The following are the important ones among them :—

1. The India Society, London.
2. Prof. Dr. S. K. Aiyangar of Madras University.
3. Dr. Coomaraswamy, Keeper of Museum of Fine Arts, Boston.
4. Mr. G. Yazdani, Director of Archaeology, Hyderabad State
5. Times of India Press through the State Political Department.
6. The Suba Sahib of Ujjain for *the Guide to Ujjain*.

Seventy-two lantern slides illustrating various antiquities were also prepared.

Sixty drawings, some complete in ink and the others in pencil were prepared. Twenty-one tracings were made for departmental reference.

For detailed list of photo-negatives, lantern slides and drawings see Appedices Nos. G, H and I.

XIII. Office Library.

One hundred and fifty volumes were added to the Office Library during the year of report, which cover divers subjects. Of these seventy were purchased and the rest were received as presents from the Government of India, Provincial Governments and the Governments of Indian States and other private Institutions to whom our thanks are due. The list of books acquired for the Library will be found in the Appendix No. J.

XIV. Income and Expenditure.

Statements of Income and Expenditure of the Department under different heads of the budget during the year of report are detailed in Appendices K and L respectively. The annual expenditure thus incurred was Rs. 26,682-7-7 and the income from different sources was Rs. 269-13-6.

XV. Concluding Remarks.

In conclusion, I am deeply grateful to Shrimant Khase Sahib Pawar and Major Sardar M. N. Shitole Sahib, the permanent and Offg. Home Members respectively, under whose able guidance, valuable advice and unflinching courtesy I could discharge the duties of this Department smoothly and successfully.

(Sd.) M. B. GARDE,
Superintendent of Archaeology,
Gwalior State.

PART II.

APPENDIX A.

**Tour Diary of the Superintendent of Archaeology, Gwalior State,
for the Year 1929-30, Samvat 1986.**

Date, month and year.	Movements and Halts.	REMARKS
November 1929. 19th-20th.	Gwalior to Bhilsa.	
20th.	Bhilsa to Besnagar, Udaygiri and back.	
20th-21st	Bhilsa to Gwalior.	
January 1930. 15th.	Gwalior to Chanderi.	
"	Chanderi to Singhpur.	
16th.	Singhpur to Chanderi and back.	
17th.	Singhpur to Mungaoli and back.	
18th.	Singhpur to Gwalior.	
21st.	Gwalior to Padhavli <i>via</i> Rithora.	
22nd.	Halt at Padhavli.	
23rd.	Padhavli to Suhania.	
24th.	Suhania to Rithora <i>via</i> Bara and Mitaoli.	
25th.	Rithora to Gwalior.	
26th-27th.	Halt at Gwalior.	
28th.	Gwalior to Gohad.	
29th.	Gohad to Bhind.	
"	Bhind to Kherhat <i>via</i> Ater.	
30th.	Kherhat to Bhind <i>via</i> Ater.	
31st.	Bhind to Bhander <i>via</i> Bara Kalan, Lahar and Daboh.	
February 1930. 1st.	Bhander to Gwalior <i>via</i> Chirgaon, Jhansi and Antri.	
11th.	Gwalior to Rithora.	
12th.	Rithora to Padhavli <i>via</i> Mitaoli and back to Rithora.	
13th.	Rithora to Gwalior.	

APPENDIX A.—(contd.)

Date, month and year.	Movements and Halts.	REMARKS.
16th.	Gwalior to Guna.	
17th.	Guna to Fatehgarh Fort.	
17th.	Fatehgarh Fort to Rampur Fort and back to Guna.	
18th.	Guna to Bajrangarh and back.	
"	Guna to Binagaon.	
19th.	Binagaon to Chanchoda and back.	
"	Chanchoda to Shajapur <i>via</i> Ghora-Pachar Bungalow.	
20th.	Shajapur to Ujjain.	
21st.	Halt at Ujjain.	
22nd.	Ujjain to Dhar <i>via</i> Mhow.	
23rd.	Dhar to Amjhera <i>via</i> Mangod.	
"	Amjhera to Bagh Inspection Bungalow.	
24th.	Bagh Inspection Bungalow to Bagh Caves and back.	
25th.	" " "	
26th-27th.	" " to Badkeshwar Mahadeva and back.	
27th.	" " to Mandasor <i>via</i> Dhar.	
28th.	Mandasor to Sondni and back.	
"	" to Achera and back.	
March 1930.		
1st.	Mandasor to Neemuch.	
2nd.	Neemuch to Singoli.	
"	Singoli to Bichor Fort and then to Makanganj.	
3rd.	Makanganj to Thakurai and then back to Singoli.	
"	Singoli to Ratangarh.	
"	Ratangarh to Jat Fort and back.	
"	Ratangarh to Neemuch.	
4th.	Neemuch to Ujjain.	
5th.	Halt at Ujjain.	

APPENDIX A.—(contd.)

Date, month and year.	Movements and Halts.	REMARKS.
6th.	Ujjain to Agar	
"	Agar to Vaijanath Mahadeva and back.	
"	" to Umarkot Fort and back.	
7th.	Agar to Shujalpur <i>via</i> Saranpur and Pachor.	
8th.	Shujalpur to Ranoganj and back.	
"	" to Binagaon.	
"	Binagaon to Chanchoda and back.	
9th.	" to Shivpuri <i>via</i> Sesai.	
10th.	Shivpuri to Tongra and back	
11th.	Shivpuri to Gwalior <i>via</i> Narwar.	
24th.	Gwalior to Padhavli <i>via</i> Rithora.	
25th.	Halt at Padhavli.	
26th.	Padhavli to Bhensoda, Amleda and back.	
27th.	" to Gwalior <i>via</i> Baraoli and Sanichara.	
28th.	Gwalior to Malipura <i>via</i> Deokho.	
29th.	Malipura to Dundapur <i>via</i> Deokho.	
30th.	Dundapur to Gwalior.	
April 1930. 7th-8th.	Gwalior to Bhilsa.	
8th.	Bhilsa to Udaypur <i>via</i> Bareth.	
9th.	Udaypur to Hamidpur <i>via</i> Bhilya.	
10th.	Hamidpur to Badoh.	
"	Badoh to Kalhar.	
11th.	Kalhar to Gwalior.	
16th.	Gwalior to Shivpuri.	
"	Shivpuri to Sirsod.	
17th.	Sirsod to Pichhor <i>via</i> Pagra.	
18th.	Pichher to Gudar.	

APPENDIX A.—(contd)

Date, month and year.	Movements and Halts.	REMARKS.
19th.	Halt at Gudar.	
20th.	Gudar to Ranod.	
21st.	Halt at Ranod.	
22nd.	Ranod to Pichhor.	
23rd.	Pichhor to Bhadarwas.	
24th.	Bhadarwas to Binagaon <i>via</i> Guna.	
"	Binagaon to Chanchoda and back.	
25th.	Binagaon to Guna.	
26th.	Guna to Gwalior.	
27th.	Gwalior to Churli near Tekanpur.	
28th.	Churli to Gwalior.	
Tour Diary of the Offg. Superintendent of Archaeology.		
May 1930.		
18th.	Gwalior to Padhavli <i>via</i> Rithora.	
19th.	Padhavli to Gwalior <i>via</i> Rithora.	
20th.	Gwalior to Nurabad.	
21st.	Nurabad to Gwalior.	
30th.	Gwalior to Naunanda	
"	Naunanda to Dhoan <i>via</i> Amkunda.	
31st.	Dhoan to Dandeki.khidak <i>via</i> Khudaoli.	
June 1930.		
1st.	Dandeki-khidak to Naunanda.	
"	Naunanda to Gwalior.	
2nd.	Gwalior to Antri.	
3rd.	Antri to Amrol.	
4th.	Amrol to Antri.	
"	Antri to Gwalior.	

APPENDIX A.—(concl.)

Date, month and year.	Movements and Halts.	REMARKS.
6th-7th.	Gwalior to Mungaoli.	
7th.	Mungaoli to Chanderi.	
8th.	Halt at Chanderi.	
9th-10th.	Chanderi to Gwalior <i>via</i> Mungaoli.	
18th.	Gwalior to Padhavli.	
19th.	Padhavli to Gwalior.	
20th.	Gwalior to Jhansi and back.	

APPENDIX B.
Statement of Monuments conserved during the Year 1929-30, Samvat 1986.

No.	Place.	Name of Monument conserved.	AMOUNT SANCTIONED.		TOTAL.	AMOUNT SPENT.		TOTAL.	REMARKS.
			Current Year.	Last Year.		Current Year.	Last Year.		
1	Bagh	Emergent repairs to caves.	Rs. 999	...	Rs. 999	Rs. a. p. 998 14 0	...	Rs. a. p. 998 14 0	
2	Bhilsa	Repairs to Khambaba.	530	...	530	528 9 0	...	528 9 0	
3	Lashkar	New work at the Chhatra of the late Maharani of Jhansi.	464	...	464	461 9 7	...	461 9 7	
4	Gwalior	Additions and alterations at the Gujarimahai building.	342	...	342	340 6 6	..	340 6 6	
5	Padhavli	Repairs to the temple in Gadhi.	773	...	773	770 14 3	...	770 14 3	
		Total	3,108	...	3,108	3,100 5 4	...	3,100 5 4	

APPENDIX C.

Monuments Listed during the Year 1929-30, Samvat 1986.

Sl. No.	Locality	Name of Monument.	Class.	REMARKS
District Amjhera.				
1	Amjhera ...	Fort with the buildings and an old gun ...	III	
District Bhilsa.				
2	Bhilaya ...	A <i>sati</i> stone lying prostrate near the end of the new tank.	"	
3	"	A <i>sati</i> stone standing near the above tank ...	"	
District Bhind.				
4	Ater ...	An inscription in a well near <i>satkhand</i> tower inside the Fort.	II.	
5	Bara ...	A group of three or four ruined temples the most notable of which is a ruined shrine of Siva to the north of the village.	III	
6	"	An old well	"	
7	"	A group of memorial pillars locally called Yoginis.	II.	
8	"	Two <i>sati</i> stones one of which is inscribed ...	III	
9	Devala ...	A <i>sati</i> monument of a Bhadauria Raja ...	III.	
10	Bara Kalan.	Pieces of a carved door-frame of an ancient temple on the road-side.	I.	
District Esagarh				
11	Bajrangarh.	Bisbhuj temple outside the town	III.	
12	"	Some old sculptures on a platform near the above temple.	"	
13	"	A small mediæval ruined shrine near above ...	"	
14	Chanchoda.	Fort	"	
15	"	Chhatri of Gosain (Bhimgir) in Fort with an inscription.	II.	
16	"	A piece of shaft of an old column, standing buried near the bank of a tank.	III.	
17	"	Bagvajesvar Mahadeva where there are some old sculptures.	"	
18	"	An old ruined shrine with carvings between Bagvajesvar and the tank.	"	

APPENDIX C.—(contd.)

No. S.	Locality.	Name of Monument.	Class.	REMARKS.
19	Chanderi.	Tomb of Captain Keatings on the Fort	...	III.
20	"	Jor Talai or Johar Tal on the Fort ...	...	"
21	"	A Christian tomb near the Delhi gate	...	"
22	Fatehgarh.	Fort ...	...	"
23	Rampur.	" ...	...	"
24	"	Inscription over the north-east gate ...	...	"
25	"	Fragments of some old sculptures outside the west wall of the Fort.	...	"
26	"	Some sculptures in a tank ...	...	"
District Gird.				
27	Amrol.	A ruined old temple called Dana-baba-ki-madhi	...	"
28	"	Old sculptures on a <i>chabutra</i> near village	...	"
29	"	Mata-ki-madhi in which old sculptures are built	...	"
30	"	Another Mata-ki-madhi ...	...	"
31	"	Ganesa Pahadi or a mound in which a big sculpture of Ganesa is lying.	...	"
32	"	Other sculptures on this mound ...	...	"
33	"	An old temple near above with sculptures and Siva <i>lingas</i> near it.	...	"
34	Churli.	Site of a ruined Siva temple with fragments of sculptures.	...	"
35	"	Site of old habitation with ruins ...	...	"
36	"	A terra cota image of a goddess (Parvati?) now removed to the Archaeological Museum.	...	"
37	"	A group of old sculptures lying on the site of an old temple.	...	"
38	"	A tall Jaina Chaumukha ...	...	II.
39	Dande-ki-khidak.	Ruins of old temples called <i>Rathas</i> at the foot of a hill near the village.	...	III.
40	"	A <i>sati</i> stone on a mound near above ...	...	"

APPENDIX C.—(contd.)

S. No.	Locality.	Name of Monument.	Class.	REMARKS.
41	"	Another group of old shrines and ruined temple in the limits of the village.	III.	
42	Jakhoda.	A ruined <i>gadhi</i>	"	
43	"	Inscribed <i>sati</i> stone near Mata-ka-temple on the side of a cart-track.	"	
44	"	A ruined Siva temple near Nala	"	
45	"	A <i>sati</i> stone near above	"	
46	Khudaoli.	A ruined old temple called <i>Ratha</i>	"	
47	Dundapura.	A group of memorial pillars on the bank of river ...	"	
48	"	A ruined Siva temple	"	
49	"	A ruined Jaina temple	"	
50	"	An inscription on a pillar in the above temple ...	"	
51	Sujwaya ...	A memorial pillar built in a <i>madhi</i>	"	
52	"	An old sculpture of Kali in a modern room near above.	"	
53	"	Another and bigger sculpture of Kali called Basai-ki-mata.	"	
54	"	A group of ruined Jaina temples and sculptures opposite the bank of a Nala.	"	
55	"	A Jaina Chaumukha in the above ruins	"	
District Mandasor.				
56	Achera.	<i>Gadhi</i>	"	
57	"	Chhatri of Chamansingh	"	
58	"	An image of Hanuman	"	
59	Bhichor.	<i>Gadhi</i> with images of Devadharma Raja and Ganesa.	"	
60	"	An image of Ganesa inscribed	"	
61	"	An inscribed stone slab planted upright	"	
62	Jat.	Fort	"	
63	Makanganj.	A group of two old ruined temples	II.	

APPENDIX C,—(contd.)

S. No.	Locality.	Name of Monument.	Class.	REMARKS.
64	Makanganj.	An inscription on one of the above temples ...	III.	
65	"	A ruined step well ...	"	
66	Manshiganj.	Ruins of a <i>gadhi</i> on a hill close by ...	"	
67	"	A ruined temple with fragments of old sculptures ...	"	
68	Morvana.	A memorial pillar outside the village ...	"	
69	"	A collection of fragments of old sculptures under a <i>nim</i> tree.	"	
70	"	Remains of an old temple...	"	
71	"	A group of <i>sati</i> stones ...	"	
72	Thakurai.	A 10th Century ruined Siva temple ...	"	
73	"	An inscribed <i>sati</i> stone near above ...	"	
74	"	Another <i>sati</i> stone inscribed to the N. W. of above.	"	
75	"	A small ruined <i>gadhi</i> ...	"	
76	Ratangarh.	Fort with various buildings ...	"	
77	"	An inscribed <i>sati</i> stone in front of Rama temple ...	"	
78	"	Old granaries ...	"	
District Narwar.				
79	Budera.	An inscribed tall column ...	II.	
80	Gudar.	A sculpture of Hanuman in Hanumankho ...	III.	
81	"	A heap of broken sculptures on a platform in Hanumankho.	"	
82	"	A ruined step-well in Hanumankho ...	"	
83	"	Sites of few old temples in Hanumankho ...	"	
84	"	A group of three ruined Hindu temples with sculptures, on the west bank of a tank.	"	
85	"	Two sites of two old tanks built with big stones in the ravine below the new tank.	"	
86	"	Sites of ruined Hindu temples to the N. W. of the village.	"	

APPENDIX C.—(contd.)

S. No.	Locality.	Name of Monument.	Class.	REMARKS.
87	Gudar.	One of the ruined temples in the above group with a tall sculpture of Vishnu known as Lachhmanji.	II.	
88	"	Another shrine standing without door-frame and <i>sikhara</i>	III.	
89	"	A tall sculpture of a goddess called Anjani in a field.	"	
90	"	Traces of a Jaina temple with a sculpture of standing Tirthamkara.	"	
91	"	A group of three Jaina Tirthamkaras standing in a field, the central one of which has an inscription on its pedestal.	I.	
92	"	A <i>sati</i> stone near above	III.	
93	"	A group of three small Hindu shrines near the village	"	
94	"	Mata's temple near Thakur's house where broken sculptures are heaped.	"	
95	"	A modern Jaina temple in the village in which pillars of old temple are built and old Jaina sculptures are sheltered.	"	
96	Nayakheda-Gudar.	An inscribed <i>sati</i> stone	"	
97	Old Gudar.	A group of <i>sati</i> stones, inscribed	"	
98	"	A tall <i>sati</i> stone, inscribed	"	
99	Sesai.	A small ruined old shrine of Siva	"	
100	"	An inscribed memorial pillar, west of the above temple.	II.	
101	"	Two old <i>sati</i> -stones near above	III.	
102	"	A ruined step-well near the south wall of <i>gadhi</i>	"	
103	"	A seated Jaina sculpture lying loose near the step-well.	"	
District Shajapur.				
104	Agar.	Sri Baijnath Mahadeva temple	"	
105	"	An old sculpture of Siva-Parvati seated on Nandi (bull) built up in above.	"	
106	"	An old image of Varaha in Varaha temple	"	
107	"	An image of Ganesa in above	"	
108	"	A tank with a <i>chhatri</i> and a <i>ghat</i>	"	
109	Shajapur.	Fort	"	

APPENDIX C.—(concl'd.)

S. No.	Locality.	Name of Monument.	Class.	REMARKS.
110	Shajapur.	Shahi garden ...	III.	
111	"	Jamah Masjid...	"	
112	"	Shahi <i>pul</i> (bridge)	"	
113	"	Shahi <i>mahal</i> (palace)	"	
114	Shujalpur.	Site and ruins of an old <i>gadhi</i>	"	
115	Umarkot.	Fort ...	"	
116	"	An inscribed pillar in Hari Mandir	"	
District Tonwarghar.				
117	Amladha.	A group of two ruined temples ...	"	
118	"	A group of two worn-out <i>sati</i> stones ...	"	
119	Ardoni.	An old well with a crocodile and channel	"	
120	"	A ruined Siva temple ...	"	
121	"	A Kamal Surya near above	"	
122	Batesvar.	A well built of big stones with monolith stone troughs.	"	
123	"	An old well with three storeyed passage	"	
124	"	Two sculptures of Nagadevas	"	
125	"	A broken memorial pillar ...	"	
126	Bharaoli.	An old temple of Siva in the village ...	II	
127	"	A group of broken sculptures near above	III.	
128	"	A group of inscribed <i>sati</i> stones	"	
129	"	An old well ...	"	
130	Bhensoda.	A ruined old Siva temple to the north of village ...	"	
131	"	Another old Siva temple to the south, along cart-track	"	
132	Nurabad.	A Persian inscription built up in a modern mosque.	"	
133	Padhavli.	Two old memorial pillars inscribed ...	II	
134	Rithora.	An inscription on the back of a memorial pillar ...	III.	

APPENDIX D.

List of Inscriptions Copied or Noticed during the Year 1929-30, Samvat 1986.

Serial No.	Locality.	Object Inscribed.	Number of Lines.	Script.	Language.	Name of King.	Date.	Purport.	REMARKS
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
		District Bhilsa.							
1	Bhilaya near Udaypur.	On a <i>sati</i> stone	6	Nagari	Hindi.	Mahmud Sultan (Tuglaq of Delhi)	V. S. 1393.	Mentions Raja Sri Mahmud Sultan, the Sati and her husband.	Not copied.
2	"	"	4	"	"	"	Magh sudi 13, Tuesday V. S. 1392.	Mentions the cremation of Sati named Ruma, wife of Lagdeva, son of <i>chaudhari</i> (name illegible) in the village Bhaitaya during the reign of Maharaja-dhiraj Mahmud.	"
3	Bhilsa ..	On an image of Seshasayi Vishnu near Bhilsa Dak Bungalow.	2	"	Sanskrit.	...	...	Text:—गौडान्वये रा श्री लाघदेवेन करापितं <i>i. e.</i> , made by Labadeva of Gauda family.	Two copies.
4	Udaypur.	On the compound wall of a mosque near Moti gate.	3	"	Hindi.	Gayas Shah.	V. S 1545 Kartika sudi 2, Monday	Records the construction of a mosque at Udaypur in the province of Chanderi when Sultan Gayas Sahi (Gayas-ud-din) was ruling at Mandapa Durga (Mandu), when Sherkhan was <i>mukhtar</i> or govern-	

APPENDIX D.—(contd.)

List of Inscriptions Copied or Noticed during the Year 1929-30, Samvat 1986.

Serial No.	Locality.	Object Inscribed.	Number of Lines.	Script.	Language.	Name of King.	Date.	Purport.	REMARKS.
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
5	Ater ...	On a wall near the temple in the fort.	4	Nagari.	Hindi	Name damaged, but the dynasty is the Bhadauriya Rajputs of Ater.	Samvat gone, Marag sudi [10], Wednesday.	or at Chanderi and when Malik Abd-Sara-Ataval was the <i>gumasta</i> or administrative agent at Udaypur. It also mentions the names of Sutradhari (architect) va ?), son of Satalu, Maharu, Punamu ?, Dalhana, Narasingh and Chhitama. Records the construction of a well by Maharaja ... Deva when Mohammad Ami was <i>daroga</i> there.	Not copied.
6	Itora ...	On a red stone pillar ...	4	"	"	...	...	... Informs the existence of life-giving (reviving) herb (संजीवन मूल) between Khajuraha and Laras Khedi.	"

APPENDIX D.—(contd.)

List of Inscriptions Copied or Noticed during the Year 1929-30, Samvat 1986.

Serial No.	Locality.	Object Inscribed.	Number of Lines.	Script.	Language.	Name of King.	Date.	Purport.	REMARKS.
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
		District Esagarh.							
7	Aketa ...	On a <i>sati</i> stone in Mata's temple.	7	Nagari.	Sanskrit (corrupt).	...	V. S. 136 [9] Magh sudi 3, Saturday.	Records the cremation of a Sati in a village named Akita. Memorial erected by Patavari Chahada ?	Three copies
8	Bajrangarh.	In the temple of twenty armed goddess.	...	"	Mara'hi.	...	V S. 1944	Refers to Kondo Krishna Limaye, a devotee of the goddess.	Not copied.
9	Chanchoda.	On a pucca platform (समाधि) of a <i>gosain</i> in the fort.	8	"	Hindi.	Vikramajit Khichi of Gugor.	...	Records the construction of a platform (समाधि) of a Gosain Bhim Girji, disciple of <i>mahanta</i> Hari Chandan Girji at Chanchora, by Maharaja Sri Vikramajit, son of Maharaja Dhirajasinghji, son of Maharaja Lalsingh of Khichi dynasty of Gugaur.	
10	Chanderi	In a niche in the southern hall of the temple of Harasiddhidevi, near Raja's Mahal	23+2 and two letters in still another line.	Nagari	Sanskrit.	Durajana Singh of Chanderi.	V. S. 1781 and 1794	The record is damaged in some places and the impression taken being not quite satisfactory; the reading of the inscription so far accomplished is tentative only.	Four copies.

List of Inscriptions Copied or Noticed during the Year 1929-30, Samvat 1986.

Serial No.	Locality.	Object Inscribed.	Number of Lines.	Script.	Language.	Name of King.	Date.	P u r p o r t .	REMARKS.
1	3	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
								<p>More definite decipherment may be possible by comparison of the original with the impression. The inscription seems to record the construction of a temple, the installation of Harasiddhi goddess by king Durjana Singh and some gift to Pandit Raghunath, younger son of Prananath, the king's religious preceptor. The genealogy of the royal family is recorded in full. It mentions the ancestors as well as the descendants of Sri Durjana Singh.</p> <p>The genealogical table is as below:— (1) Kasi Raja of the family of Bhairava, the founder of the dynasty, is styled as <i>Samrat</i>—Emperor, (2) his successor Ram Sahi, (3) his grandson Bharatesa, (4) his son Devi Simha, (5) his son Durga Simha, (6) his son Durjana Simha, (7) his eldest son Manasimha who is also known as <i>yuvaraja</i>.</p>	

APPENDIX D.—(contd.)

List of Inscriptions Copied or Noticed during the Year 1929-30, Samvat 1986

Serial No.	Locality.	Object Inscribed.	Number of Lines.	Script.	Language.	Name of King.	Date.	P u r p o r t .	REMARKS.
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
11	Chanderi.	In a niche in front of <i>Tilsi Ghara</i> in Raja's Maqbara (monument) near Par. mesra Tal.	4	Nagari,	Incorrect Sanskrit and Hindi.	...	V. S. 1765.	<p>Then seems to follow a list of names of persons apparently of the same royal family, whose exact relationship cannot be made out. They are (1) Sri Raja Simha, (2) Sri Dhira Simha, (3) Sri Vishnu Simha, (4) Sri Bahadura Kumara, (5) Sri Gopala Simha and (6) Sri Jaya Simha. Then follows the name of Gorelal, a well-wisher of the king, who claims to have engraved this inscription on the temple of Harasiddhi and of Jeta Simha (a Kayastha?) who appears to be the writer.</p> <p>Records the construction of the <i>samadhi</i> (memorial platform) of a <i>sadhu</i> named Surati Rama who passed away to Vakuntha (Vishnu's heaven). The first three lines of the inscription are engraved above and the last line below the footprints of the <i>sadhu</i> who seems to be a follower of the cult of Rama as the record opens with a salutation to that god.</p>	Three copies.

APPENDIX D —(contd.)

List of Inscriptions Copied or Noticed during the Year 1929-30, Samvat 1986.

Serial No.	Locality.	Object Inscribed.	Number of Lines.	Script.	Language.	Name of King.	Date.	P u r p o r t .	REMARKS.
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
12	Chanderi.	On a step-well in Houja khasa.	7	Naskh.	Persian.	Mahmud Shah Khilji of Mandu.	The figure showing year is worn-out. Month is Ramzan.	Records the construction of a mosque in the reign of Mahmud Khilji of Mandu. Date is illegible.	Two copies. Removed to Arch. Museum.
13	"	On a loose slab which was brought from Pranpur near Chanderi by Devi Chaukidar.	7	"	Persian.	Ibrahim Lodi.	A. H. 902 Ramzan.	Records the construction of a well (with steps) by.....(name illegible), son of Kamal, during the reign of Ibrahim Shah, son of Sikandar Shah Lodi.	"
14	Rampur.	On a stone stuck up over the inner face of the N. E. gateway of the fort	A big square.	Nagari Sanskrit	...	...	...	The inscription is a square consisting of five rows of five squares each, thus making 25 squares in all. The five squares forming the central vertical and the central horizontal rows are inset with a letter each, and this makes one vertical and one horizontal word of letters. The letters having been damaged, the words cannot be made out with certainty. Each of the remaining 16 squares contains a numerical figure,	Two copies.

APPENDIX D.—(contd.)

List of Inscriptions Copied or Noticed during the Year 1929-30, Samvat 1986.

Serial No.	Locality.	Object Inscribed.	Number of Lines.	Script.	Language.	Name of King.	Date.	P u r p o r t .	REMARKS.
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
15	Dande-ki-khidak	On a <i>sati</i> stone ...	6	Nagari	Hindi	...	V. S. 1564, Savan sudi 9.	Illegible.	which are so arranged that any four squares taken vertically, horizontally or diagonally but symmetrically to the central lines make the sum of 170. This seems to be one of the magic squares and is locally believed to be a spell with the effect that the cattle passing through the gate over which it is engraved are immune to disease.
16	Jakhoda.	On a <i>sati</i> stone ...	3	"	"	...	V. S. 1 [4] 75.	"	
17	"	" near a ruined temple.	13	"	"	...	...	Refers to Devi Jasoda.	

APPENDIX D.—(contd.)

List of Inscriptions Copied or Noticed during the Year 1929-30, Samvat 1986.

Serial No.	Locality.	Object Inscribed.	Number of Lines	Script.	Language.	Name of King.	Date.	P u r p o r t .	REMARKS.
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
18	Bhichor.	District Mandasor. On a slab (शिलालेख) near an image of Ganesa about 1½ miles from Bhichor on the Bhichor-Makanganj Road	16	Nagari	Hindi.	...	...	It records the names of various artisans and workmen from the village of Bhichor, who came to the spot to collect material for the construction of a well or <i>baori</i> for Sri ka (ki) an Kwarji, mother of Ravat Devi Singhji of Begu	Not copied.
19	Jat.	On a copper-plate in the possession of Prabhulal Tekchand Gujar, Gauda Brahmana of Jat	...	"	"	Maharaja Rajasingh of Begu (?)	...	Records the grant of 31 bighas of land to Tiwari Baswan by Maharaja Sri Ravat Rajasinghji.	
20	Makanganj.	On a slab in a niche of a ruined temple.	14	Nordic characters about 7th or 8th century.	Sanskrit	...	No date has been preserved in the existing portion.	The inscription is extremely damaged and all but completely lost. It must have recorded the history of the construction of the shrine on which it is engraved. A few words which are still decipherable contain two names of Dattasimha and his son Gopasimha, perhaps the members of the genealogy of the then ruling dynasty or of the donor's family.	Two copies.

List of Inscriptions Copied or Noticed during the Year 1929-30, Samvat 1986.

Serial No.	Locality.	Object Inscribed.	Number of Lines.	Script.	Language.	Name of King.	Date.	P u r p o r t .	REMARKS
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
21	Mandasor.	On a loose slab from a well at Mandasor (Now in possession of Miss B. Filose, daughter of Sir M. Filose).	25	Gupta.	Sanskrit.	Yasodharman and Vishnuvardhan.	..	The object of the inscription is to record the construction of a large well by a person named Daksha, the younger brother of Dharmadasha, who was a minister of Vishnuvardhana, in memory of the deceased uncle Abhayadatta who had formerly held the same office for the tract of country bounded by the Vindhya and Pariyatra mountain and the western ocean. It refers to the reign of Yasodharman.	Four copies published in Ind. Ant., Vol. XV, Pp. 222 and Fleet's <i>Gupta Inscriptions</i> , P. 150, plate XXII.
22	Thakurai	On a <i>sati</i> pillar near the old ruins of a temple.	4	Nagari	Hindi.	..	V. S. 1—9 Jestha sudi 5	Records the cremation of a <i>sati</i> named Indradevi, wife of a Brahmana named Arjuna. The two middle digits of the number expressing the year have peeled off. The memorial was erected by Upadhaya Gopasuta (son of Gopa).	
23	Budhera	District Narwar. On a stone post on a hillock near Jhaloni Tank in the limits of Budhera village	7	Nagari	Hindi	Padma Raja	V. S. 1351, Saka 1216.	Refers to Kirti Durga and mentions Padmaraja who is endowed with the royal title of <i>Samasta-Rajavali-Samalan-</i>	

APPENDIX D.—(contd.)

List of Inscriptions Copied or Noticed during the Year 1929-30, Samvat 1986.

Serial No.	Locality.	Object Inscribed.	Number of Lines.	Script.	Language.	Name of King.	Date.	P u r p o r t .	REMARKS.
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
24	Gudar.	On a <i>sati</i> stone about 1½ miles to the east of Gudar.	10+1 in margin.	Nagari	Hindi.	Sultan Gayas-ud-din of Mandu	V. S. [1] 5 [7] 3 Kartika sudi 9	<i>kriṭa-Parama-Bhataraka</i> . Other names which can be read are Udai Simha and his son (Hari, Raja, etc. Being badly written and partially damaged its object is not clear. A <i>sati</i> record, refers to Sher Khan, governor of Chanderi, under Sultan Gayas-ud-din of Mandugarh.	
25	"	On another <i>sati</i> stone on the way to Jhaloni tank 1½ miles to the east of Gudar.	10+1 in margin.	"	"	Sultan Hosang Shah.	V. S. 1485 —Vadi 3, Wednesday.	Refers to Hosang Shah of Mandugarh and Chanderi Desa. It is badly written and is almost illegible.	
26	"	On the right jamb of the door-frame of a temple on the western bank of a tank at Gudar.	10	"	Sanskrit.	...	...	The object of the record is not clear. Some letters and numerical figures are written in lines and they have been, as it were summed up and the sum is given below as [16411]. The letter (५) appears to have been repeated in each line	Three copies

APPENDIX D.—(contd.)

List of Inscriptions Copied or Noticed during the Year 1929-30, Samvat 1986.

Serial No.	Locality.	Object Inscribed.	Number of Lines.	Script.	Language.	Name of King.	Date.	P u r p o r t .	REMARKS.
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
27	Gudār.	On a <i>sati</i> stone on the site of a ruined village (old Gudār) near Gudār.	11	Nagari.	Hindi.	...	V. S. 1476 Magh sudi 13, Sunday.	Records the cremation of <i>sati</i> Mahade, daughter of (Ratuga), with her dead husband Dyanganadeva, son of Sri Dilhadeva, an inhabitant of village Gudar in the province of Chanderi, during the reign of Kadari Khan. Dilhadeva is described as a pious man who had just returned from the pilgrimage of Prayag (Allahabad). The cremation appears to have taken place on the bank of the Betava near the Chanchoda Ghat which is about 5 or 6 miles from the spot where the <i>sati</i> pillar now stands.	
28	"	On the pedestal of the biggest one of the three Jaina statues in a field at Gudār.	7	Nagari.	Sanskrit (corrupt).	...	V. S. 1206 Ashadha vadi 9, Wednesday	Records the construction of three images of the Jains, Shantinatha, Kunthanatha, and Aranatha by Gange Dharma Deva, son of Sadhu Guna Chandra and his wife Galha of the Lavakanchuka race. The object of installing the idols is recorded as attainment of special merit and destruction of Karma	Two copies.

APPENDIX D.—(contd.)

List of Inscriptions Copied or Noticed during the Year 1920-30, Samvat 1986.

Serial No	Locality.	Object Inscribed.	Line No.	Script.	Language.	Name of King.	Date.	REMARKS.
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	10
29	Nayagaon near Gadar.	On a stone pillar	13	Nagari.	Hindi.	Moham- mad Ghazni.	V. S. 144 (5).	Refers to the reign of Mohammad Ghazni. But this appears to mean Mohammad Tughalak of Delhi as the latter fits in with the date. It also men- tions Gahakhan Dilawar of Chanderi. The name of the village is given as Kuidaha. The writer was Udharana, He and his son Maharaja planted (erected) the pillar.
30	Pachrai.	On a smaller <i>sati</i> stone to the east of Pachrai near <i>Zilmil</i> <i>baori</i> .	5	"	"	...	V. S. 1362.	A <i>sati</i> record; much damaged and names illegible.
31	"	On another tall <i>sati</i> stone east of Pachrai near <i>Zilmil baori</i> .	7	"	"	...	V. S. 1374 Kartika vadi 12.	A <i>sati</i> record; mentions Ghadal, son of Nalahada, as the dead husband. Name of <i>sati</i> is not clear.
32	"	"	7	"	"	...	V. S. [1383] Magba vadi 3	A <i>sati</i> record; much damaged and illegible.
33	"	On a fallen <i>sati</i> stone to the east of Pachrai.	8	"	"	...	V. S. (1319).	" "

APPENDIX D.—(contd.)

List of Inscriptions Copied or Noticed during the Year 1929-30, Samvat 1986.

Serial No.	Locality.	Object Inscribed.	Number of Lines.	Script.	Language.	Name of King.	Date.	P u r p o r t .	REMARKS.
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
34	Pachrai.	On the central tall <i>sati</i> stone to the east of Pachrai.	9	Nagari.	Hindi.	..	V. S. (1339).	Mentions Chanderi Desa It is much damaged and illegible.	Two copies.
35	"	" "	10	"	"	Sultan Gayas. ud.din.	V. S. 137-(?)	Refers to Sultan Gayas-ud-din. All else is illegible due to damaged condition.	
36	Pagra.	On a <i>sati</i> stone on the old site of Pagra village.	...	"	"	..	V. S. 17-(?) Magha sudi 15.	The name of <i>sati</i> given is Hari-kuwar.	Not copied.
37	Sesai.	Two lines above and one line below a panel of sculpture on a memorial pillar	3	Gupta.	Sanskrit.	..	...	Records that some Brahmama youths were killed in a battle with..... and their bereaved mother (name peeled off and illegible) cremated herself in sorrow.	Three copies.
38	Umarkot.	District Shahapur. On a slab near the temple of Hara, Part A. Part B.	15 21	Nagari.	Hindi.	Doulat Rao Maharaj	V. S. 1877 Saka 1763 Jeth sudi 15, Monday.	Records the installation of the image of Rama in the village named Umarkot, when Rana Jalim Singh held his sway there under a vassal chief Kishor Singh,	
			36						

APPENDIX D.—(contd.)

List of Inscriptions Copied or Noticed during the Year 1929-30, Samvat 1986.

Serial No.	Locality.	Object Inscribed.	Number of Lines.	Script.	Language.	Name of King.	Date.	P u r p o r t .	REMARKS
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
39	Shajapur.	In the Jamma Masjid ...	2	...	Persian.	...	A. H. (108).	Mir Hyder Ali, Buikler Mir Kalan.	Not copied
								<p>who is styled Maharajahiraja during the regime of Maharaja Daulat Rao. The names of contributors are as under:—</p> <p>Panchameratawala Mahajan, Saha Kaniramji, Saha Rupachandji, Ram Bagasji, Saha Bakhatramji, Saha Gangaramji, Saha Maniramji of Julanya, Saha Lekhorajaji of Bhandari Gota. The artisans who were employed are Brahman Syamjibhai Ankar Baswan of Ajaya? It records the name of Ramchandji who took the lead in the installation and was in turn assisted by Pancholi Lachhmi Narain and Thakur Bhopala Singhji.</p>	

APPENDIX D.—(concl'd.)

List of Inscriptions Copied or Noticed during the Year 1929-30, Samvat 1986.

Serial No.	Locality.	Object Inscribed.	Number of Lines.	Script.	Language.	Name of King.	Date.	P u r p o r t .	REMARKS.
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
40	Nurabad	District Tonwarghar. Stuck up in a modern mosque outside the <i>sarai</i> .	3	Nas-taliq.	Persian.	...	A. H. 1072	Records the construction of the mosque in the time of Aurangzeb.	Two copies.
41	Padhavli.	On a slab of a wall in <i>gadhi</i> .	14	Nagari	Sanskrit (corrupt).	...	V. S. 1584 Marag vadi 4.	Records a certain name who composed the two verses. Being incorrectly written they are uninterpretable.	Two copies.
42	Rithora.	On a <i>sati</i> stone ...	8	Old Nagari.	...	...	...	Totally damaged and illegible.	Four copies.
43	Gwalior Fort.	District Gird. On a slab in the Sun temple.	6	Northern Gupta	Sanskrit.	Mihirakula.	...	Refers to the reign of Mihirakula. It also records the construction of a temple of Surya.	Published in Fleet's <i>Gujia Inscriptions</i> p. 161, pl. XXIII.

APPENDIX E.

List of Coins Examined during the Year 1929-30, Samvat 1986.

S.No.	Name of King.	Mint.	Metal.	Specimen.	REMARKS.
1	(Yadava Dynasty of Devagiri) Singhana II.	...	Gold.	1	
2	(Vijayanagar Dynasty) Hari Hara II	...	"	Half Pagoda 1	
3	" Deva Raya II.	...	"	Pagoda 1	
4	" Krishna Raya.	...	"	" 1	
5	" "	...	"	Half Pagoda 1	
6	Indo-Sassanian of crude type ...	...	Silver.	22	
7	" " ...	...	Copper.	242	
8	Aurangzeb ...	Etawah.	Silver.	10	
9	" ...	Agra.	"	1	
10	" ...	...	"	4	
11	Farrukh Siyar ...	Gwalior.	"	1	
12	Muhammad Shah ...	Delhi.	"	8	
13	" ...	Kota.	"	1	
14	" ...	Surat.	"	1	
15	" ...	Murshidabad.	"	1	
16	" ...	...	"	8	
17	Shah Alam II ...	...	"	6	
	Total ...	...	...	310	

APPENDIX F (i).

List of Antiquities added to the Archaeological Museum, Gwalior Fort,
during the Year 1929-30, Samvat 1986.

Serial No.	Find-spot.	Description.	Size.
Inscriptions.			
1	Mandasor.	A stone inscription in Nagari characters.	2'4" x 1'3"
2	Chanderi.	A stone inscription in Nastaliq characters.	2'2" x 2'
3	"	" " "	2' x 2'
4	Mandasor	Impression of the Mandasor well inscription of Yasodharman and Vishnuwardhana (stone is in the possession of Miss Filose at Lashkar).	
5	"	Impression of an inscription of Mihirakula on the Surya Temple, Gwalior Fort (now in Indian Museum, Calcutta).	
Sculptures.			
6	Padhavli.	Chaumukha Siva	2'10" x 1'6½"
7	"	Lakulisha	2'10" x 2'8"
8	"	A male and a female devotee ...	2'3" x 1'6"
9-12	"	Three heads and one limb	
13	Churli.	Terra cotta image of a goddess ...	18'2" x 10"
Paintings.			
14	...	A man standing, trying to cut a branch of a tree, an elephant and a huge snake (Ajagara) (a metaphorical representation of the wordly life of a man).	14" x 10"
15	...	A lady seated closely wrapped up, addressing a maid standing before her.	8½" x 6¾"
16	...	A lady standing, under a flowering tree, holding a branch of the tree, facing left and with a maid servant standing at her back carrying a <i>hukka</i> .	8½" x 5½"
17	...	A board on which are pasted different views of the palace (Rajwada) of Maharaja Mahadji Scindhia at Jamgaon, District Ahmadnagar.	2½' x 1¾'
Coins			
18	...	Gold coin of Yadava Dynasty of Devagiri.	1
19-22	...	Gold coins of Vijayanagar Dynasty ...	4

APPENDIX F (ii).

List of Antiquities collected for the Archaeological Museum, Ujjain,
during the Year 1929-30, Samvat 1986.

Serial No.	Find-spot.	Description.	Size.
1	Ujjain.	Siva (locally called Kapila) ...	9 $\frac{1}{4}$ ' x 3'
2	"	Siva Parvati seated ...	1'2" x 10"
3	"	Siva Parvati marriage (polished) ...	2'4" x 1'6"
4	"	Siva Parvati seated ...	1'10" x 1'3"
5	"	" ...	1'4" x 1'
6	"	" ...	1'2" x 9"
7	"	Siva Parvati standing under a tree ...	4'10" x 2'3"
8	"	Siva Parvati standing ...	2'8" x 1'8"
9	"	Rudra ...	3' x 2'
10	"	Bhairava (?) ...	1'6" x 1'7"
11	"	" ...	2' x 1'11"
12	"	Ganesa dancing ...	2'11" x 1'10"
13	"	" seated ...	2'9" x 1'9"
14	"	" " ...	1'8" x 1'
15	"	" " ...	1'8" x 1'
16	"	" " ...	2' x 1'6"
17	"	Parvati in a niche ...	3'7" x 1'7"
18	"	" " ...	2'10" x 1'7"
19	"	A goddess ...	2'2" x 1'2"
20	"	Kali (tempered within later times) ...	5'4" x 1'9"
21	"	" " " ...	1'10" x 1'1"
22	"	Trimurti (Bust) ...	2'9" x 2'
23	"	Trimurti (seated) ...	1'2" x 1'4"
24	"	Nairiti seated (?) ...	1'9" x 1'10"
25	"	Vishnu standing with incarnations in the <i>Prabhavalaya</i> .	4'3" x 2'3"

APPENDIX F (ii).—(concl'd.)

Serial No.	Find-spot.	Description.	Size.
26	Ujjain.	Vishnu standing... ..	2'10" × 1'9"
27	"	" "	4'9" × 2'
28	"	Seshasayi Vishnu	2'7" × 1'9"
29	"	" "	4'4" × 1'6"
30	"	Lakshmi Narayan on Garuda	2'2" × 1'
31	"	Surya seated (cross legged) in a niche	1'1" × 1'6"
32	"	Naga (upper half human and lower serpent)	2' × 1'3"
33	"	" " " "	2'10" × 1'5"
34	"	Head and canopy of Jaina Tirthamkara.	1'11" × 2'4"
35	"	A male devotee and his consort	1'7" × 1'
36	"	Brahma standing in a niche... ..	1'9" × 1'
37	"	A god seated (damaged)	1'6" × 1'6"
38	"	A fragment of Varaha (animal)	1'7" × 1'3"
39	"	A bracket with Hindi and Persian inscription.	
40	"	A Sanskrit inscription from Madhava College, Ujjain.	
41	"	A goddess (Ganga ?) standing	2'5" × 1'5"
42	"	Nandi	1'7" × 7"

APPENDIX G.

List of Photographs taken during the Year 1929-30, Samvat 1986.

S. No.	Locality.	Object and description.	Size	REMARKS
District Amjhera.				
1	Amjhera.	A building in the interior of Fort	Half.	
2	"	Another building in the interior of Fort	"	
3	"	Chandika and Ambika temples after clearance	"	
4	Bagh.	Fort	"	
5	"	Cave No. 2, facade after repair, from N. E.	Full.	
6	"	" " " " S. W.	"	
7	"	Cave No. 4, facade showing wooden shutters on fresco paintings, from S. W.	"	
8	"	" " facade after repairs from S. W.	Half	
9	"	" " Naga Raja chapel	"	
10	"	" " " " (another view)	"	
District Bhilsa.				
11	Besnagar.	Khambaba, from south	Full.	
12	"	" " S. E.	"	
13	"	" " N. E.	"	
14	"	" " north	"	
15	Udaypur.	Bird's-eye-view of Udayeshwar temple from east.	Half	
District Bhind.				
16	Bara.	Old memorial pillars locally known as Yoginis	Quar- ter.	
17	"	Two old memorial pillars near above		
18	Barakalan.	Loose pieces of door-frames, g. v.	Half.	
19	"	Loose pieces of temple	"	
20	"	" " " " " "	"	
21	Bhind.	Main entrance gate of Nawadabag, g. v.	Full.	
22	"	" " " " near view	"	

APPENDIX G.—(contd.)

S. No.	Locality.	Object and description.	Size.	REMARKS.
23	Bhind.	Kacheri building in Nawadabag	Half.	
24	Gohad.	Entrance gate of Nayamahal from west ...	Full.	
25	"	" " " " another view ...	"	
26	"	Lambert's tomb	Quarter.	
27	"	Christian soldier's tomb in Bankipura, locally known as Gora.	"	
28	Gohadi.	A Christian tomb	"	
District Esagarh.				
29	Bajrangarh.	Twenty armed goddess	Half.	
30	Chanchoda.	A piece of the shaft of a column on the bank of a tank, before excavation.	"	
31	"	A piece of the shaft of a column on the bank of a tank, after excavation.	"	
32	"	Fort, partial view	"	
33	Fatehgarh.	Fort, general view from north-west ...	"	
District Gird.				
34	Amrol.	A ruined old temple	"	
35	"	Pillars of another old ruined temple ...	"	
36	Bhander.	A Sanad in possession of a Fakir, descendent of Baba Kapur.	Quarter.	
37	"	Above Sanad and some relics of Baba Kapur in possession of the Fakir.	"	
38	Churli.	A Jaina Chamukha	"	
39	Gwalior.	Tomb of Tansen from east	Full	
40	"	Muhammad Ghaus' Tomb (Jali panels) ...	"	
41	"	" " " " " " ...	"	
42	"	" " " " " " ...	"	
43	"	" " " " " " ...	"	
44	"	" " " " " " ...	"	

APPENDIX G —(contd.)

S. No.	Locality.	Object and description.	Size.	REMARKS.
45	Gwalior.	Mohammad Ghau's Tomb (Details of brackets and pillars).	Full.	
46	"	" " (Southern Verandah).	"	
47	"	Fort, general view from Moti Mahal ...	"	
48	"	Archæological Museum, Varaha (animal form) ...	"	
49	"	Archæological Museum, Double Lion Bracket ...	Half.	
District Mandasor.				
50	Achera.	Gadhi, general view ...	"	
51	Bhichor.	" ...	"	
52	Jat.	" ...	Quar- ter.	
53	Makanganj.	An early mediæval temple ...	Half.	
54	"	Another old temple ...	Quar- ter.	
55	Morban.	A collection of fragmentary loose images ...	"	
56	Thakuri.	A ruined Siva temple ...	Half.	
57	Singoli.	Gadhi ...	"	
District Narwar.				
58	Gudar.	A group of big Jaina images standing in a field...	"	
59	"	A goddess locally called Anjani ...	Quar- ter.	
60	"	Shrine (half ruined) without <i>shikhar</i> or door- frame.	"	
61	Pagra.	Fragments of old sculptures on a prominence near road-side,	"	
District Shajapur.				
62	Agar.	Vaijanatha Mahadeva temple ...	Half.	
63	Shajapur.	Main gateway of Fort ...	Quar- ter.	
64	Umarkot.	Panoramic view of Fort ...	Half.	
65	"	" " ...	"	
66	"	Chhatri in the Fort ...	"	

APPENDIX G.—(contd.)

S. No.	Locality.	Object and description.	Size.	REMARKS.
District Tonwarghar.				
67	Mitaoli.	Ekottarso Mahadeva temple, partial view of cells.	Half.	
68	"	Ekottarso Mahadeva temple, view of some other cells.	"	
69	Padhavli.	Gadhi, Kachheri, north-east portion ...	Full.	
70	"	Gadhi, Kachheri, north-west portion ...	"	
71	"	Gadhi, sculptures kept against the western portion retaining wall after clearance.	Half.	
72-74	"	Gadhi, sculptures kept against the western portion retaining wall after clearance.	"	
75	"	Gadhi, a memorial pillar in the same collection ...	"	
76	"	Gadhi, temple before clearance from S. W. ...	Full.	
77	"	Gadhi, near view after clearance from S. W. ...	"	
78	"	Gadhi, distant view from S. W. ...	"	
79	"	Gadhi, near view after clearance from N. W. ...	"	
80	"	Gadhi, interior pillars ...	"	
81	"	Interior pillars and panels, in Gadhi ...	"	
82	"	Gadhi, Temple, sculpture of Kali ...	Half.	
83	"	" whole panel of Kali...	Full.	
84	"	" sculpture of Siva-Parvati ...	Half.	
85	"	" whole Siva-Parvati panel ...	Full.	
86	"	" sculpture of Surya ...	Half.	
87	"	Whole panel of Surya ...	Full.	
88	"	Sculpture of Brahma ...	Half.	
89	"	Sculpture of Siva ...	"	
90	"	Sculpture of Vishnu ...	"	
91	"	Gadhi, Temple, sculptures of Brahma, Vishnu and Siva.	Full.	

APPENDIX G.—(contd.)

S. No.	Locality.	Object and description.	Size.	REMARKS.
92	Padhavi.	Gadhi, detail of panel A	Full.	
93	"	" " B	"	
94	"	" " C	"	
95	"	" " D	"	
96	"	" " E	Half.	
97	"	" " F	"	
98	"	" " G	"	
99	"	" " H	"	
100	"	" " I	"	
101	"	" " J	"	
102	"	" " K	"	
103	"	" " L	"	
104	Rithora.	Ancient memorial pillars in a group	"	
105	"	Another memorial pillar in the same group	"	
106	Suhania.	Kakanmadh temple, g. v. from S. E.	Full.	
107	"	" " " "	Half.	
108	"	" " near view from south	Full.	
109	"	" " near view from east	"	
110	"	" " near view from north-east.	"	
111	"	" " detail of southern side	"	
District Ujjain.				
112	Ujjain.	Image of Vishnu now in the collection at the Mahankala Temple, Ujjain.	Half.	
Miscellaneous.				
113	Arch. Museum.	A princess standing under a flowering tree attended by her maid.	Half.	
114	"	Another princess seated covering herself closely as if with cold and addressing her maid.	"	

APPENDIX G.—(contd.).

S. No.	Locality.	Object and description.	Size.	REMARKS.
115	Arch. Museum,	A metaphorical representation of worldly life ...	Full.	
116	"	A Maratha Warrior on horse back ...	"	
(Indian Historical Records Exhibition, 1930, held at Gwalior (Local Section).				
117	...	A group of old arms artistically exhibited ...	Full.	
118	...	" " " "	"	
119	...	" " " "	Half.	
120	...	" " " "	"	
121	...	A group of old arms artistically exhibited ...	"	
122	...	" " " "	"	
123	...	A copper plate inscription ...	"	
124	...	Copies of an exhibit having (a) obverse of a Farman reg. a village in Pargana Nurabad, dated 2nd Safar in the 44th Regnal year (b) obverse of a Farman reg. Ghauspura, dated 2nd Safar in the 44th Regnal year.	Full.	
125	...	Copies of an exhibit having (a) Reverse of the Farman of a village in Nurabad Pargana detailed in Negative No. 124 A.	"	
125	...	(b) Reverse of the Farman of Ghauspura detailed in the Negative No. 124 B.	"	
126	...	Copies of an exhibit having (a) Obverse of a Farman reg. Ghauspura, dated 17th Jamadi-ul-sani in the 9th Regnal year.	"	
126	...	(b) Obverse of another Farman reg. Ghauspura, dated 14th Shaban in the 17th Regnal year, 1053 A. H.	"	
127	...	Copies of an exhibit having (a) Reverse of Farman detailed in Negative 125 A.	"	
128	...	(b) Reverse of Farman detailed in Negative 125 B.	"	
129	...	Obverse of a Farman reg. village Bolia, Pargana Kiampur, District Mandasor, dated 14th Muharram in the 49th Regnal year.	"	

APPENDIX G.—(concl.)

S. No.	Locality.	Object and description	Size.	REMARKS.
130	...	Copies of exhibits having (a) Reverse of Farman reg. Bolia detailed in Negative No. 127 (b) Obverse of Takid Patra of Maharaja Ranoji Rao Scindia.	Full.	
130	...	Copies of exhibits (a) Obverse of a Takid Patra of Maharaja Ranoji Rao Scindia. (b) Obverse of a Farman reg. village Khanukheda Distric Mandasor, dated 14th Muharram, in the 47th Regnal year	,	
131	...	Copies of exhibits (a) Reverse of a Farman of Khanukheda detailed in Negative No. 129 B. (b) Reverse of a Takid Patra detailed in Negative No. 130 A.	"	
132	...	Copies of exhibits having (a) Obverse of a Farman reg. village Khamkhedi, Pargana Dhakoni, District Chanderi, dated 29th Jamadi-ul-Sani, in the 9th Regnal year.	"	
133	...	Copies of exhibits having (a) Reverse of the Farman of Khamkhedi detailed in Negative No. 132 showing endorsements. (b) Do showing a seal and another endorsement. (c) Painting of Tansen	" " "	
Foreign Section.				
134	...	Painting : Battle of Prithvi Raj Chauhan (Rai Pithora) with Muhammad Ghor.	"	
135	...	Painting : Nava Ratna Darbar of Akbar ...	"	
136	...	" " " " another ...	"	
137	...	" " " " Shahjahan ...	"	
138	...	" " " " Darbar of Akbar II ...	"	
139	...	" " " " of Maharaja Daulat Rao Scindia.	"	
140	...	" " " " of a Rajput king ...	"	
141	...	Painting of Baz Bahadur and Rup Mati ...	"	
142	...	" " " " of Jahangir at study ...	"	
143	...	" " " " Maharani Lakshmi Bai of Jhansi.	"	
144	...	" " " " a prince on horse-back reviewing his horse troops	"	
145	...	A map of India showing places having charitable institutions founded by Ahilyabai Holkar.	"	
146	...	A map of India showing ancient shrines and monuments	"	

APPENDIX H.

List of Lantern Slides made during the Year 1929-30, Samvat 1986.

S.No.	Locality.	Object and description.	REMARKS.
District Amjhera.			
1	Bagh.	Cave No. 2, interior pillars.	
2	"	" " a door-keeper.	
3	"	" 4 wooden shutter protection for fresco paintings on facade.	
4	"	" " interior range of pillars.	
5	"	" " a pilaster.	
6	"	" " carving on a window.	
District Bhilsa.			
7	Besnagar.	Khambaba or Heliodoros pillar.	
8	"	" another view.	
9	Bhilsa.	Charana Tirth.	
10	Gyaraspur	Torana gateway.	
11	"	Atha Khamba.	
12	"	Side view of Maladevi temple.	
13	Udaygiri.	Cave No. 3, <i>Linga</i> with a face.	
14	"	" 5, Seshasayi.	
15	"	" " Earth goddess	
16	"	" " Ganga and Yamuna.	
17	Udaypur.	Udayesvar temple, Eastern medallion.	
18	"	" Western "	
19	"	" Southern porch.	
20	"	" Carving (specimen).	
21	"	" "	
22	"	" <i>Sikhara</i> (top) only.	
23	"	" View from South.	
24	"	" Vedi.	

APPENDIX H.—(contd.)

S.No.	Locality.	Object and description.	REMARKS.
25	Udaypur.	Udayesvar temple Northern attendant shrine.	
26	"	" " Shahi Mahal, a Jali panel.	
27	"	" " " " another Jali panel.	
28	"	" " Mosque, interior view.	
29	Badoh.	Gadarmal temple, general view.	
30	"	" " Porch.	
31	"	A ruined torana.	
District Bhind.			
32	Ater.	A statue of Raja Badansingh.	
33	"	Satkhandia tower on Fort.	
34	Gohad.	Naya Mahal, interior.	
District Esagarh.			
35	Chanderi.	Fort, general view.	
36	"	" " Delhi Darwaza.	
37	"	" " Badal Mahal gate.	
38	"	" " A carved tomb stone.	
39	"	Bada madarsa.	
40	"	Koshak Mahal, general view.	
41	"	" " Arches.	
42	"	Jamah Masjid.	
43	"	A carved mihrab of a tomb.	
44	Kadwaha	Temple No. 3.	
45	"	" " Nos. 3 and 4, general view.	
46	"	Hindu monastery, general view.	
District Gird.			
47	Gwalior.	Tomb of Tansen.	
48	"	Tomb of Muhammad Ghaus.	

APPENDIX H.—(concl'd.)

S.No.	Locality.	Object and description.	REMARKS.
49	Gwalior.	Tomb of Muhammad Ghaus Jali, panels,	
50	"	" " " "	
51	"	" " " "	
52	"	" " " " a corner.	
53	"	Fort, Jaina images at Urwahi gate.	
54	"	" Telika mandir (oilman's temple).	
55	"	" two Sas Bahu temples, general view.	
56	"	" larger Sas Bahu temple, interior pillars.	
57	"	" " " dome.	
58	"	" Man Mandir, distant view.	
59	"	" " east face near view.	
60	"	" " ceiling of theatre room.	
61	"	" Gujari Mahal, general view.	
62	"	" Archæological Museum, Sarasvati from Suhania.	
63	"	" " " Vishnu from Suhania.	
64	"	" " " a female figure from Suhania.	
65	"	" " " flying figure from Sondni.	
66	"	" " " Yasoda and Krishna.	
67	"	" " " Torso from Pawaya.	
68	"	" " " Bell capital from Bhilsa.	
69	"	" " " piece of a lintel from Pawaya.	
70	"	" " " Manibhadra image from Pawaya.	
71	"	" " " Lion capital from Udaygiri.	
72	"	" " " " " "	

APPENDIX I.

List of Drawings prepared during the Year 1929-30, Samvat 1986.

S.No.	Locality.	Object and description.	Scale.	REMARKS.
		District Amjhera.		
1	Amjhera	Plan of Fort	1" = 60'	Tracing from the copy belonging to the Military Department.
2	Bagh	"	"	"
3	Bakaner	"	"	"
4	Lalgath	"	"	"
5	Manawar	"	"	"
6	Tanda	"	1" = 50'	"
		District Bhilsa.		
7	Bhilsa	Plan of Fort	1" = 200'	Printed copy received from the Military Department.
8	"	Plan of Bijamandal mosque	1" = 8'	In pencil.
9	Udaypur	Plan of Udayesvar temple	1" = 4'	Complete in ink.
10	"	Block plan of Udayesvar temple	1" = 16'	"
11	"	Detail of Vedi and an attendant shrine	1" = 4'	"

S.No.	Locality.	Object and description.	Scale.	REMARKS.
12	Ater	Plan of Fort	1" = 100'	Printed copy from Military Department.
13	Bhind	"	"	"
14	Gohad	"	"	"
15	"	"	"	" Dup.
District Esagarh.				
16	Bajrangarh	Plan of Fort	1" = 200'	Printed copy from Military Department.
17	Chanchoda	"	1" = 100'	"
18	Chanderi	"	1" = 400'	"
19	Fatebgarh	"	1" = 500'	"
20	Esagarh	"	1" = 200'	"
21	Jalalpur	"	1" = 50'	"
22	Malbargarh	"	1" = 200'	"
23	Rampur	"	1" = 100'	"

APPENDIX I.—(contd.)

S.No.	Locality.	Object and description.	Scale.	R M M A R K S .
		District Gird.		
24	Bhitarwar and Lachhmangarh.	Plan of Fort ...	1"=100'	Printed copy from the Military Department.
25	Chhatargarh ...	" ...	"	"
26	Deogarh ...	" ...	1"=100'	"
27	Gwalior ...	Site plan of Rani Jhansi's Chhatri	1"=12'	Complete.
28	" ...	Plan of Gujari Mahal (Fort) ...	1"=8'	"
29	" ...	Cellar of Gujari Mahal (Fort) ..	1"=4'	"
30	Himmatgarh ...	Plan of Fort ...	1"=100'	Printed copy from Military Department.
31	Mastura ...	" ...	1"=50'	"
32	Pawaya ...	" ...	1"=200'	"
		District Mandasor.		
33	Achera ...	Plan of Fort ...	1"=50'	Tracing from copy in the Military Department.
34	Bhaugarh ...	" ...	1"=30'	"
35	Bhichor ...	" ...	1"=20'	"
36	Gwalior Kalan.	" ...	1"=30'	"

APPENDIX I.—(contd.)

S.No.	Locality.	Object and description.	Scale.	REMARKS.
37	Jat	Plan of Fort	1" = 50'	Tracing from copy in the Military Department.
38	Jeeran	"	1" = 60'	"
39	Lasur	"	1" = 20'	"
40	Mandasor	"	1" = 100'	"
41	Ratangarh	"	1" = 150'	"
42	Singoli	"	1" = 30'	"
District Narwar.				
43	Bara	Plan of Fort	1" = 200'	"
44	Gopalpur	"	1" = 400'	"
45	Karera	"	1" = 200'	"
46	Narwar	"	1" = 200'	"
47	Pichhore	"	1" = 100'	"
48	Pohari	"	1" = 200'	"
49	Rajgarh	"	1" = 60'	"
50	Surwaya	"	1" = 100'	Printed copy from the Military Department.

APPENDIX I.—(concl'd.)

S.No.	Locality.	Object and description.	Scale.	REMARKS.
51	Bijeypur	Plan of Fort	1" = 100'	Printed copy from the Military Department.
52	Sheopur	"	1" = 200'	"
53	Ranod	Plan of Fort	1" = 40'	Tracing from copy in the Military Department.
54	Nalkheda	"	1" = 50'	"
55	Shajapur	"	1" = 50'	"
District Tonwarghar.				
56	Jawahargarh	Plan of Fort	1" = 100'	Printed copy from the Military Department.
57	Sabalgarh	"	1" = 200'	"
58	Parichha	"	1' = 25'	"
District Ujjain.				
59	Badnagar	Plan of Fort	1" = 50'	Tracing from the copy in the Military Department.
60	...	A map of Gwalior State showing important places of Archaeological interest.	1" = 16 miles.	Tracing.

APPENDIX J.

List of Books added to the Office Library of the Superintendent of Archaeology, Gwalior State, during the Year 1929-30, Samvat 1986.

S. No.	Title of book.	REMARKS.
Archaeological Survey Reports and Memories.		
1	Annual Report of the Mysore Archaeological Department, for the year 1928.	Presented by Mysore Darbar.
2	Annual Report of the Archaeological Department of the Cochin for the year 1927-28, by Anujan Achan.	Presented by Cochin Darbar.
3	Annual Report of the Archaeological Department of H. E. H. the Nizam's Dominions, for the year 1919-20.	Presented by Nizam Darbar.
4	Annual Report of the Archaeological Department of H. E. H. the Nizam's Dominions, for the year 1920-21.	"
5	Annual Report of the Archaeological Department of H. E. H. the Nizam's Dominions, for the years 1921 to 1924.	"
6	Annual Report of the Archaeological Department of H. E. H. the Nizam's Dominions, for the year 1924-25.	"
7	Annual Report of the Archaeological Department of H. E. H. the Nizam's Dominions, for the year 1925-26.	"
8	Annual Report of the Archaeological Department of H. E. H. the Nizam's Dominions, for the year 1926-27.	"
9	Annual Report of the Watson Museum of Antiquities, Rajkot, for the year 1929-30.	"
10	Memoir No. 39 Lha-lun Temples, Sypiti, by A. H. Francke.	Presented by Government of India.
11	" 40 Pallava Architecture, Part III, by Longhurst.	"
12	" 41 Survival of the prehistoric civilisation of the Indus Valley by R. Chanda.	"
13	Antiquities of Sind by Dr. Cousens	"
Art and Architecture.		
14	Bulletin of the Museum of Fine Arts, Boston, for June 1929.	Gratis.

APPENDIX J.—(contd.)

S. No.	Title of book.	REMARKS.
15	Die Indische Kunst by Dr. Stella Kramrisch ...	Purchased.
16	Ipeak by Dr. A. K. Coomaraswamy ...	Gratis.
17	Indian Music and its Instruments by E. Rosenthal ...	Purchased.
18	The A. B. C. of Indian Art by J. F. Blacker ...	„
19	Indian Art and Letters Vol. III, No. 1, by India Society.	Gratis.
20	Chinese Art by R. L. Hobson ...	Purchased.
21	Oriental Art by R. Kæchlin and G. Migeon ...	„
22	The Splendour that was Ind. by K. T. Shah ...	„
23	Indian Art and Letters, Vol. III, No. 2 ...	Gratis.
24	Mural Paintings of the Bombay School by Capt. Gladstone.	Purchased.
25	A Chinese Buddhist Water Vessel and its Indian Prototype by Dr. Coomaraswamy.	Gratis.
Books and Bibliography.		
26	Annual Bibliography of Indian Archaeology for the year 1928 by Kern Institute, Leyden.	Purchased.
Dictionaries.		
27	A Dictionary of Hindoostanee and English by Capt. J. Taylor.	Purchased.
28	Shri Bharatvarshiya Prachin Itihasik Kosha by Godbole	„
29	A Dictionary of Urdu into Hindi published by Bhargava.	„
30	Hindi Dictionary by Babu Sardarsingh ...	„
Epigraphy.		
31	Epigraphia Indica, Vol. XIX, No. VI, for April 1928.	Gratis.
32	Epigraphia Indo-Moslemica 1925-26 by G. Yazdani.	„
33	Epigraphia Indica, Vol. XVIII, No. VIII ...	„
34	The New Asokan Edict of Maksi by Arch. Dept., Hyderabad.	„

APPENDIX J.—(contd.)

S. No.	Title of book.	REMARKS.
35	Munirabad Stone Inscription of the 13th year of Tribhuvanamalla (Vikramaditya VI) by Arch. Dept., Hyderabad.	Gratis.
36	The Kotagiri Plates of the reign of the Kakatiya Queen Rudramamba, A. D. 1273 by Arch. Dept., Hyderabad.	"
37	Bodhan Stone Inscription of the reign of Trailokyamalla Somesvara I (A. D. 1056) by Arch. Department, Hyderabad.	"
38	The Inscription of Nagai by Arch. Dept., Hyderabad.	"
39	Annual Report on South Indian Epigraphy for the year ending 31st March 1928.	"
Guides.		
40	कन्दार by Y. R. Gupte	Purchased.
41	My Journey to Parali by Y. R. Gupte	"
42	Guide map of Ellora caves published by the Survey of India Office.	Gratis.
43	Guide map of Ajanta caves published by the Survey of India Office.	"
44	Fortress of Gwalior by Major E. B. Keith ...	Purchased.
History.		
45	Mediæval Hindu India, Vol. III, by C. V. Vaidya ...	"
46	The Main Currents of Maratha History by G. S. Sardesai.	"
47	History of Rajputana, Vol. III, by G. H. Ojha ...	"
48	The Primitive Culture of India by Col. T. C. Hodson.	"
49	The Heart of India by L. D. Barnett	"
50	History of Burma by G. E. Harvey	"
51	शिंदेशाही इतिहासाची साधने भाग १ ला, आनंदराव भाऊ फाळके कृत.	"
52	History of the Kayasthas	"
53	मराठी रियासत उत्तर विभाग १ सवाई माधवरावचा पूर्वयुक्रम गो. स. सरदेसाई कृत.	"
54	" " २ सवाई माधवरावचा उत्तरयुक्रम गो. स. सरदेसाई कृत.	"

APPENDIX J.—(contd.)

S. No.	Title of book.	REMARKS.
55	Mahadji Scindia of Gwalior by A. F. M. Abdul Ali ...	Gratis.
56	The Historical Exhibition held at Nagpur in 1928 by A. F. M. Abdul Ali.	"
57	Historical Gleanings by B. C. Law	Purchased.
58	History of the Armenians in India by M. J. Seth ...	"
59	Jaina Historical Studies by Umrao Singh Tank ...	"
60	South India and her Muhammadan Invaders by S. K. Aiyangar.	"
61	The Beginnings of South Indian History by S. K. Aiyangar.	"
62	Biographies of Shivaji by Surendra Nath Sen ...	"
63	Birth Date of Shivaji by D. V. Apte and Paranjpe ...	"
64	Shivaji Album by Dr. Balkrishna	"
65	शिव कालीन पत्र सार संग्रह खंड १	"
66	" " २	"
67	शिवाजी निबंधावली भाग १	"
68	" " २	"
69	संपूर्ण भूषण	"
70	शिव कथा कुसुम गुच्छ पुष्प ५ वें सेवा रहस्य श्रीमंत बाळा साहेब पंत प्रतिनिधी कृत.	"
71	सचित्र शिव चरित्र भाग १	"
72	" भाग २	"
73	" भाग ३	"
74	शिव चरित्र साहित्य खंड भाग १ ला. क. वा. पुंढरे कृत	"
75	" भाग २ रा पोतदार व मुजुमदार कृत	"
76	" भाग ३ रा जोशी व खरे कृत	"
77	" निबंधावली अष्टकम २	"
Ethnography.		
78	India by Dr. D. R. Bhandarkar	"

APPENDIX J.—(contd)

S. No.	Title of book.	REMARKS.
Iconography.		
79	The Gods of Northern Buddhism by Alice Getty ...	Purchased.
80	Hindu Gods and Heroes by L. D. Barnett ...	"
Journals and Periodicals.		
81	Index to Indian Antiquary, Vol. LVIII, 1929 ...	"
82	Indian Antiquary for January 1911 ...	"
83-94	Indian Antiquary from July 1929 to June 1930 ...	"
95-106	Modern Review from July 1929 to June 1930 ...	"
107-109	Indian Historical Quarterly, Vol. V, Nos. 2, 3 and 4.	"
110	" " " VI, No. 1 ...	"
111-114	Journal of the Mythic Society Vol. XX, Nos. 1 to 4 ...	"
115	Journal of Indian History, Vol. VIII, Part I, by S. K. Aiyangar.	"
116	Journal of the Andhra Historical Research Society, Vol. IV, Parts 1 and 2.	Gratis.
117-119	भारत इतिहास संशोधक मंडळ, पुणे, Vol. X, Nos. 1, 2 and 3.	Purchased.
120-122	काशी नागरी प्रचारिणी पत्रिका, Vol. X, Nos. 3, 4 and " IX, No. 4.	"
123-125	त्याग भूमि, Vol. 3, Nos. 3 ...	Gratis.
Literature.		
126	संस्कृत कवि पंचक, 3rd edition, by विष्णुशास्त्री चिन्मूलकर ...	Purchased.
127	Introduction to Prakrit by A. C. Woolner ...	"
128	Vasavadatta of Subandhu by Louis H. Gray ...	"
129	दाता महाराव शाह वली का तजकिरा by वि. गि. राखे ...	Gratis.
130	श्री रघुनाथ देव महाराज यांचे चरित्र by वि. गि. राखे ...	"
131	The Holy Quran by Maulvi Muhammad Ali, M. A. ...	Purchased.
132	व्यवहार पत्रादर्श पिनाकीलाल व पितांबरलाल कुत ...	"
133	साधन माला भाग १ ला मद्राचार्य कुत ...	"
134	" भाग २ रा " ...	"

APPENDIX J.—(concl'd.)

S. No.	Title of book.	REMARKS.
135	पंचम सम्मेलन वृत्त शके १८३९ of भारत इतिहास संशोधक मंडळ पुणे.	Purchased.
136	Mahabharat Adiparva Fascile No. 4 by Sukhrankar	"
137	Some Contributions of South India to Indian Culture by Dr. S. K. Aiyangar.	"
138	The Tale of Tulsi Plant and other studies by C. A. Kincaid.	"
Miscellaneous.		
139	Gardening by W. W. Johnstone	"
Museum.		
140	Bulletin of the Madras Government Museum (The flowering plants of Madras City and its immediate neighbourhood) by P. W. Mayuranathan.	Gratis
141	Do. (The littoral Fauna of Krussdia Island in the Gulf of Manner by various authors).	"
142	Bulletin of the Museum of Fine Arts, Boston, for June 1930.	"
143	Do. Madras Government Museum by T. N. Ramchandran.	"
Numismatics.		
144	Catalogue of the coins in the Indian Museum, Calcutta, Vol. IV, Native States by J. Allan.	Purchased.
Religion and Mythology.		
145	Buddhist Birth Stories by T. W. R. Davids ...	"
State Publications.		
146	The General Statistics of the Gwalior State for Samvat 1977.	Gratis.
147	The Selections of Council Orders for Samvat 1984 ...	"
148	Administration of the Gwalior State, 1926-27 ...	"
149	The General Statistics of the Gwalior State for Samvat 1978.	"
150	Muafi Department Pat for Samvat 1985 ...	"

APPENDIX K.

Statement of Expenditure incurred during the Year 1929-30, Samvat 1986.

Serial No.	Head.	AMOUNT SPENT.		Total.
		Current year.	Last year.	
		Rs a. p.	Rs. a. p.	Rs. a. p.
1	Salaries	11,664 12 5	...	11,664 12 5
2	T. A.	2,348 15 9	...	2,348 15 9
3	Contingencies	1,448 5 5	...	1,448 5 5
4	Books	394 13 6	...	394 13 6
5	Miscellaneous	489 10 6	...	489 10 6
6	Publication	1,499 11 3	399 12 0	1,899 7 3
7	General saving, current year ...	154 12 0	...	154 12 0
8	Museum	1,789 7 9	...	1,789 7 9
		Rs. a. p.		
	(a) Salaries	300 0 0		
	(b) Upkeep of building.	98 15 0		
	(c) Collection and upkeep of antiquities	1,190 9 3		
	(d) Collection of antiquities for Ujjain Museum.	199 15 6		
		1,789 7 9		
9	Works.—			
	(a) Salaries	444 0 0	...	444 0 0
	(b) Conservation proper ...	3,100 5 4	...	3,100 5 4
	(c) Upkeep of monuments already conserved.	644 11 3	...	644 11 3
	(d) Excavation	149 3 0	...	149 3 0
	(e) Miscellaneous	721 0 3	978 14 0	1,699 14 3
10	Expenditure over and above budget grant (famine allowance of the staff).	454 1 2	...	454 1 2
	Total Expenditure ...	25,303 13 7	1,378 10 0	26,682 7 7

APPENDIX L.

Statement of Income realised during the Year 1929-30, Samvat 1986.

S. No.	Head.	Amount.	REMARKS.
		Rs. a. p.	
1	By sale of photographs ...	17 3 0	
2	„ tender forms ...	3 0 0	
3	„ books ...	240 12 0	
4	Miscellaneous ...	8 14 6	
	Total ...	269 13 6	

(a) Loose pieces of a temple door-frame at Bara Kalan (general view).

(b) Loose pieces of a temple door-frame at Bara Kalan (near view).

(a) Nawadabagh at Bhind : Main entrance (near view).

(b) Tomb of Tansen at Gwalior.

(a) A ruined old temple at Amrol.

(b) A double lion bracket
(in the Arch. Museum at Gwalior).

(c) A Jaina *Chaumukha* at Chiroli.

(a) Two Christian tombs at Gohad.

(b) Varaha (animal form) from Badoh (now in the Arch. Museum at Gwalior).

(a) Muhammad Ghaus' tomb at Gwalior : *Jali* panels.

(b) Muhammad Ghaus' tomb at Gwalior : *Jali* panels
(another view).

[The text in this section is extremely faint and illegible. It appears to be a list or index of items, possibly including titles and authors, but the characters are too light to transcribe accurately.]

(a) A group of Jain images at Gudar.

(b) Two early mediæval temples at Makanganj (general view).

(c) An early mediæval temple at Makanganj (near view).

(a) Temple in *Gadbi* at Padhavli, before conservation.

(b) Temple in *Gadbi* at Padhavli, after conservation.

(a) Temple in *Gadbi* at Padhavli : Panel of Siva and Parvati.

(b) Temple in *Gadbi* at Padhavli : Panel showing Brahma, Siva and Vishnu.

(a) Temple in *Gadbi* at Padhavli : Surya panel.

(b) Temple in *Gadbi* at Padhavli : A panel of sculpture.

(a) Temple in *Gadhi* at Padhavli: Panels of sculpture.

(b) A metaphorical representation of worldly life (a painting in the Arch. Museum at Gwalior).

(c) A princess with her maid (a painting in the Arch. Museum at Gwalior).

A.

"A book that is shut is but a block"

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